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Global overview of the spread and impact of H5 clade 2.3.4.4b high pathogenicity avian influenza virus in wildlife, 2020-2024

OFFLU *ad-hoc* group on global impact

Lead authors:

Andrew Breed: Epidemiology, Surveillance and Laboratory Section, Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry, Canberra, Australia. andrew.breed@aff.gov.au

Lineke Begeman: Department of Viroscience, Erasmus University Medical Centre, Rotterdam, The Netherlands.

Jolene A. Giacinti: Ecotoxicology and Wildlife Health Division, Science and Technology Branch, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Government of Canada, Burlington, Ontario, Canada.

Julianna B. Lenocho: United States Department of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service, Wildlife Services, Fort Collins, Colorado, USA.

Manabu Onuma: National Institute for Environmental Studies, Tsukuba City, Ibaraki, Japan.

Laura C. Roberts: Department of Agriculture, Western Cape Government, Elsenburg, Western Cape, South Africa.

Marcela M. Uhart: Karen C. Drayer Wildlife Health Center, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of California, USA.

Yoshi Sakoda: Laboratory of Microbiology, Department of Disease Control, Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan.

David E. Stallknecht: Southeastern Cooperative Wildlife Disease Study, Department of Population Health, The University of Georgia, Athens, Georgia, USA.

Ralph E.T. Van Streels: Karen C. Drayer Wildlife Health Center, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of California, USA.

Michelle Wille: WHO Collaborating Centre for Reference and Research on Influenza, at the Peter Doherty Institute for Infection and Immunity, Melbourne, Australia; Department of Microbiology and Immunology, at the Peter Doherty Institute for Infection and Immunity, Melbourne, Australia.

Thijs Kuiken: Department of Viroscience, Erasmus University Medical Centre, Rotterdam, The Netherlands. t.kuiken@erasmusmc.nl

Contributing authors:

Stephanie Avery-Gomm: Wildlife Research Division, Wildlife and Landscape Science Directorate, Science and Technology Branch, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Government of Canada, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada.

Francesca Baldinelli: European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy.

Yohannes Berhane: National Centre for Foreign Animal Disease, Canadian Food Inspection Agency, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada.

Sarah N. Bevins: United States Department of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service, Wildlife Services, Fort Collins, Colorado, USA.

Alessandro Broglia: European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy.

Michael Brown: Wildlife Management and Regulatory Affairs Division, Canadian Wildlife Service, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Government of Canada, Gatineau, Quebec, Canada.

Ruth Cromie: CMS FAO Co-Convened Scientific Task Force on Avian Influenza and Wildlife/COP-Appointed Councillor for Wildlife Health, Bristol, United Kingdom.

Jorge E. De la Torre-Miguel: Mexico–United States Commission for the Prevention of Foot and Mouth Disease and other Exotic Diseases of Animals (CPA-DGSA-SENASICA), Mexico City, Mexico.

Ana V. Fonseca-Delgado: Mexico–United States Commission for the Prevention of Foot and Mouth Disease and other Exotic Diseases of Animals (CPA-DGSA-SENASICA), Mexico City, Mexico.

Alice Fusaro: European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL) for Avian Influenza and Newcastle Disease, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie (IZSVe), Legnaro, Italy.

Armando García-López: Mexico–United States Commission for the Prevention of Foot and Mouth Disease and other Exotic Diseases of Animals (CPA-DGSA-SENASICA), Mexico City, Mexico.

Damien Joly: Canadian Wildlife Health Cooperative, Western College of Veterinary Medicine, Saskatoon, Saskatchewan, Canada.

Megan Jones: Canadian Wildlife Health Cooperative - Atlantic Region, Atlantic Veterinary College, University of Prince Edward Island, 550 University Ave, Charlottetown, Prince Edward Island, Canada.

Lisa Kohnle: European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy.

Andrew Lang: Department of Biology, Memorial University of Newfoundland, St. John's, Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada.

Kimberly M. Pepin: United States Department of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service, Wildlife Services, Fort Collins, Colorado, USA.

Wendy Puryear: Department of Infectious Disease and Global Health, Cummings School of Veterinary Medicine at Tufts University, North Grafton, Massachusetts, USA.

Margo Pybus: Alberta Environment and Parks, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada.

Gregory J. Robertson: Wildlife Research Division, Wildlife and Landscape Science Directorate, Science and Technology Branch, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Government of Canada, Mount Pearl, Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada.

Anthony V. Signore: National Centre for Foreign Animal Disease, Canadian Food Inspection Agency, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada.

Mario Solís-Hernández: Mexico–United States Commission for the Prevention of Foot and Mouth Disease and other Exotic Diseases of Animals (CPA-DGSA-SENASICA), Mexico City, Mexico.

Trevor Thompson: Wildlife Management and Regulatory Affairs Division, Canadian Wildlife Service, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Government of Canada, Gatineau, Quebec, Canada.

Héctor E. Valdez-Gómez: Mexico–United States Commission for the Prevention of Foot and Mouth Disease and other Exotic Diseases of Animals (CPA-DGSA-SENASICA), Mexico City, Mexico.

Jonas Waldenström, Linnaeus University, Kalmar, Sweden.

Richard Webby: Department of Infectious Diseases, St Jude Children's Research Hospital, Memphis, Tennessee, USA.

Mitzunari Zalapa-Hernández: Mexico–United States Commission for the Prevention of Foot and Mouth Disease and other Exotic Diseases of Animals (CPA-DGSA-SENASICA), Mexico City, Mexico

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Abstract

There is an ongoing and expanding panzootic of clade 2.3.4.4b of the Goose/Guangdong lineage high pathogenicity avian influenza (HPAI) H5 that involves many wild species of birds and mammals, as well as domestic and captive animals and humans. Since the virus adapted to more efficient transmission in wild birds in 2020-2021, the HPAI H5 panzootic has shown an unprecedented geographic expansion and a continuously growing host range. Outbreaks have been often associated with high mortality rates thus representing an additional conservation threat to some wildlife populations already under multiple pressures. Existing surveillance systems are inadequate to accurately monitor spread and document impacts of HPAI H5 in wildlife, leading to insufficient data to inform appropriate mitigating or preventative actions. The aim of this report is to review HPAI H5 spread and impacts in wildlife between October 2020 and September 2024, summarise current HPAI H5 surveillance systems in wildlife per continental region and provide recommendations for future preparedness and response.

Our review showed that systems for surveillance of HPAI H5 in wildlife worldwide are based mainly on activities for detection of virus in wild birds found sick or dead, and much less on activities for detection of virus in apparently healthy wild birds or mammals. HPAI H5 was present in wildlife during the entire reporting period (October 2020 to September 2024) in the continental regions of Asia, Middle East, Europe and Africa. During this period, HPAI H5 was first reported in North America in November 2021, spreading southward to South America in October 2022, and to the Subantarctic/ Antarctic region in October 2023, disseminating rapidly in wildlife of those regions. HPAI H5 had not been reported in Oceania by September 2024.

The highest number of detections of HPAI H5 in wildlife in the Americas were made in the first year after incursion. In subsequent years in North America, and during the entire reporting period in Europe and Asia, there were seasonal peaks of HPAI H5 detection in waterfowl during autumn migration and winter aggregation, and in seabirds during spring and summer breeding. The seasonal dynamics of HPAI H5 in wildlife could not be inferred for other affected continental regions because of insufficient data. In the northern hemisphere, high numbers of HPAI H5 detection in wild birds were associated with more virus detections in wild mammals. Severe mortality events due to HPAI H5 impacted populations of many wild bird species (mainly waterfowl, seabirds and raptors) in all affected continental regions, as well as populations of several pinniped species in the Americas, and the Subantarctic / Antarctic region.

Analysis of viral genomes provided evidence to infer spread patterns, including the geographical sources of new introductions. Generation and analysis of serological data, which was not a core component of most HPAI surveillance programmes, provided complementary insights on the spread and impact of HPAI H5 not evident from virus detection and mortality data.

Worldwide recommendations for improving surveillance and understanding impacts include: developing collaborative (flyway-based if appropriate) HPAI surveillance programmes in wild birds and mammals; better estimation and reporting of wildlife mortality events associated with HPAI to an international database such as the World Animal Health Information System; improving sharing of surveillance data; and conducting long-term monitoring of severely impacted wildlife populations. Recommendations for better outbreak prevention and supporting wildlife population resilience include: increasing surveillance efforts and timely reporting of detections, reducing additional threats to, and improving conditions for, wildlife populations at risk or impacted from HPAI H5; and developing policies to prevent recurrent outbreaks of HPAI in poultry and farmed mammals, and spillover into wildlife.

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Introduction

The long-distance spread of Goose/Guangdong-lineage high pathogenicity avian influenza (HPAI) H5 viruses has increased from occasional movements between Asia, Europe, the Middle East and Africa (2005-2014) to more frequent intercontinental spread as well as establishment in North America, Central America, the Caribbean, South America and Antarctica (Annex I). This change is associated with the emergence of clade 2.3.4.4b of H5 viruses which seem particularly fit to maintain in wild bird populations and through wild bird migration and movements have caused a panzootic. This clade has spread further, infected a larger number of wild bird and mammal species and had greater impacts on wildlife than ever before. While some data on the spread and impact of HPAI in wildlife are available in reports to the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) (available via the World Animal Health Information System (WAHIS)) and scientific literature, we currently lack a globally representative analysis and overview. We also lack a surveillance system to adequately monitor and measure the impacts of HPAI on wildlife which impairs capabilities for appropriate preparedness and response. Given the anthropogenic nature of the emergence and establishment of Goose/Guangdong lineage viruses and the current biodiversity crisis, mitigations and strong response activities are crucial. Herein we aim to describe the recent global spread and impact of HPAI H5 viruses in wildlife, consider limitations in the underlying health surveillance, and provide recommendations for future preparedness and response.

We used publicly available data from the WOAH and the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO), peer-reviewed journal articles and government websites to summarise the spread patterns and impact of HPAI H5 on wildlife for each continent since 2020. Where possible we described the reported HPAI H5 outbreak events by 'epidemiological year' as strong seasonal patterns are evident in available data for most continents. Interpretation of patterns observed in available data are limited by various biases including variation in surveillance coverage, sampling approaches and reporting processes. Limitations in health surveillance systems to provide representative data on the presence and impact of HPAI on wildlife have been highlighted previously [1-5]. In particular, many sources of data reviewed indicated the number of HPAI H5 detections in wild animals found dead and tested, rather than the total number of wild animals found dead; consequently, absence of reporting of large scale mortality may not represent absence of large scale mortality. We comment on the relevant health surveillance activities and associated data quality for the purposes of informing geographic spread patterns and impacts on wildlife. Finally, we provide recommendations for consideration in planning future health surveillance activities and response to HPAI outbreaks in wildlife.

Definitions & Acronyms

Throughout this overview the categories of wild bird groups used are:

- 1) **Waterfowl**, consisting of the order Anseriformes, which includes ducks, geese and swans.
- 2) **Raptors**, consisting of the orders Accipitriformes (including buzzards, hawks and eagles), Cathartiformes (New World vultures), Falconiformes (falcons) and Strigiformes (owls).
- 3) **Colony-breeding seabirds**, defined for the purpose of this report as Alcidae (auks), Laridae (including gulls and terns), Pelecanidae (pelicans), Suliformes (including boobies, gannets, cormorants, shags and frigate birds), Procellariiformes (including albatrosses, petrels and shearwaters), and Stercorariidae (skuas).
- 4) **Other birds**, consisting of the remaining avian species.

Epidemiological year: October to September

Throughout this overview the months indicated by the different seasons per section are:

	Asia, Europe, North and Central America	Africa, Antarctica, Oceania, South America,
Spring	March to May	September to November
Summer	June to August	December to February
Autumn	September to November	March to May
Winter	December to February	June to August

List of Acronyms

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
HPAI: High Pathogenicity Avian Influenza
LPAI: Low Pathogenicity Avian Influenza
WAHIS: World Animal Health Information System
WOAH: World Organisation for Animal Health

Asia

Introduction

This section describes HPAI infection in wildlife in Asia (Annex I) from October 2020 to September 2024. For this analysis, data was used from EMPRES-I (downloaded on 29 Nov 2024). Seven countries had data available: Japan, the Republic of Korea, India, the People's Republic of China, Chinese Taipei, Nepal, and Cambodia. Information on HPAI in Russia was added as a separate addendum at the end of the section.

Spread patterns and impact

During the timeframe of this study, 1,948 detections of avian influenza cases (both high and low pathogenicity) were reported in Asia in poultry, wildlife or environmental samples. Of these, 727 detections were recorded as HPAI in wildlife: 464 detections from Japan, 202 from the Republic of Korea, 26 from India, 20 from the People's Republic of China, 12 from Chinese Taipei, 2 from Nepal, and 1 from Cambodia (Figure 1). However, clade or lineage information was not consistently available for all detections.

Among the 727 detections, large-billed crow (English and scientific names of all bird and mammal species mentioned in the text are provided in Annex II), was the most frequently recorded ($n = 190$). These reports were associated with mass mortality events of crows (both large-billed and carrion) in an urban park in Hokkaido in March to May 2022, March to April 2023, and January to April 2024, from HPAI H5N1 [6], and in January 2024 (85 large-billed and carrion crows found dead) from HPAI H5N1 and HPAI H5N5 [7]. There were 90 reported detections of infection among raptors. The raptor species most frequently reported infected were: white-tailed eagle, peregrine falcon, and eastern buzzard. Detections of infection in raptors were reported mainly from Japan. There were 239 reported detections of infection among waterfowl. The waterfowl species most frequently reported infected were: whooper swan, mallard, and mandarin duck.

Detections of infection in waterfowl were reported from both Japan and Republic of Korea with no indication of mass mortality from the data. The reported detections also included colony-breeding seabirds, such as the herring gull, brown-headed gull, and whiskered tern again without reports of mass mortality events in breeding colonies.

Figure 1. HPAI H5 detections in wildlife in Asia from October 2020 to September 2024. Data source: EMPRES-I

Detections were reported in the following species: red-crowned crane; listed as Endangered in the IUCN Red List [8]), black-faced spoonbill (Endangered), hooded crane (Vulnerable), white-naped crane (Vulnerable), and Steller's sea eagle (Vulnerable). Particularly noteworthy is the frequent occurrence of H5N1 infections in hooded cranes and white-naped cranes from 2022 to 2023 (36 detections registered in EMPRES-i+). These reported detections correspond to an unusual mortality event of 1,425 hooded and 79 white-naped cranes in the Izumi Plain, Japan, during the 2022–23 winter season, which was confirmed to be due to HPAI H5N1 [9]. Japan serves as an important wintering ground for these species. Therefore, from the perspective of endangered species conservation, discussions are underway on potential disease control measures in their wintering habitats, including intentional dispersal at crane wintering sites to avoid excessive concentration of birds in a single location and prevent new outbreaks [9] (Table 1).

There have been four reported detections of infection in mammals, all from Hokkaido, Japan. HPAI H5N1 was isolated from the carcass of an Ezo red fox in March 2022, from the carcass of an Ezo raccoon dog, in April 2022, and from the carcasses of two Ezo red foxes in February and April 2023. It is likely that these mammals were infected by consuming wild birds that were infected with HPAI H5N1.

Table 1. List of bird species with 10 or more reported detections from October 2020 to September 2024.

Species	Number
Large-billed crow (<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>)	190
Whooper swan (<i>Cygnus cygnus</i>)	76
Mallard (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)	37
Hooded crane (<i>Grus monacha</i>)	37
White-tailed eagle (<i>Haliaeetus albicilla</i>)	27
Mandarin duck (<i>Aix galericulata</i>)	26
Peregrine falcon (<i>Falco peregrinus</i>)	21
Eastern buzzard (<i>Buteo japonicus</i>)	18
Great white egret (<i>Ardea alba</i>)	15
Mute swan (<i>Cygnus olor</i>)	14
White-naped crane (<i>Grus vipio</i>)	12
Eurasian wigeon (<i>Anas penelope</i>)	10

In 2020, H5N8 was the predominant subtype combination of HPAI detected. From 2021 onwards, HPAI H5N1 became the dominant subtype combination. From 2023 onwards, HPAI H5N5, HPAI H5N6 and HPAI H5N2 also were isolated from wildlife in addition to HPAI H5N1. The number of detections of subtype combinations were: H5N1, 435 detections; H5N2, 1 case; H5N5, 35 detections; H5N6, 18 detections; H5N8, 175 detections; H5Nx, 46 detections; and HPAI of unknown subtype, 16 detections (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Monthly detections reported of HPAI in wildlife in Asia from October 2020 to September 2024, indicating subtypes involved (Excluding 30 detections missing occurrence date information). Data source: EMPRES-I

The temporal pattern of detections showed clear seasonality, with annual epidemics starting around October or November, peaking between November and March, and ending around April or May (Figure 3). Of the recorded detections, 64% (464 of 727 detections, all birds except for four mammals) were reported from Japan, and 28% (202 out of 727 detections, no mammals reported) were from the Republic of Korea, with detections from these two countries accounting for 92% of the total. Hence the seasonal pattern observed in these data may be representative of the epidemiology in these two countries and not necessarily elsewhere in Asia.

Figure 3. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in Asian countries that regularly reported (Republic of Korea and Japan), by week of suspicion (the week when an HPAI case is first suspected; dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird groups in epidemiological years: (a) 2020-2021 (b) 2021-2022 (c) 2022-2023 and (d) 2023-2024 (up to May). Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections: 699. Data source: EMPRES-I.

In general, waterfowl begin their southward migration from more northerly breeding grounds in areas such as Siberia from late July onwards into September to arrive in wintering sites such as Japan around October, then leaving from late February onwards to return north to breeding areas, arriving around April/May of the following year [10-12]. Studies in Japan have reported that the positivity rate for avian influenza virus detections in faeces (HPAI and, or LPAI) peaks during early migration and the first part of the wintering period (October to December) and gradually declines thereafter [13]. The main bird species from which avian influenza viruses have been detected in faecal samples are the mallard, eastern spot-billed duck and the northern pintail [13]. Furthermore, a study on avian influenza virus detection from wild birds in Japan demonstrated that the abundance of migratory dabbling ducks, particularly mallards, at the time of sampling is a major factor influencing virus detection from wild bird surveillance [14]. Hence the arrival of waterfowl, especially dabbling ducks, increases the probability of virus introduction and spread, leading to the seasonal occurrence pattern of HPAI in Japan. In fact, an analysis of the genotype of viruses isolated in Japan during 2022–2023 revealed that the same lineage of HPAI virus was isolated from waterfowl such as mallard, Eurasian wigeon and greater white-fronted goose, as well as from resident birds such as peregrine falcon and large-billed crow [15]. Since the wintering grounds of waterfowl are widely distributed across temperate Asia, the seasonal occurrence of HPAI in wildlife across temperate Asia can be at least partially attributed to the migratory patterns of waterfowl, particularly dabbling ducks.

A summary of annual occurrences of high pathogenicity avian influenza in each country is presented in Table 2.

Surveillance and data quality

The available data used here are from EMPRES-i+, which incorporates official reports to WOA and data from national authorities. These data indicate that many countries in Asia have some form of avian influenza surveillance in wildlife. However, various limitations and gaps are evident which preclude interpretation of spread patterns and impacts in wildlife populations across all of Asia. Some detections reported lack complete information on host species and date and the total number of animals that have died is usually missing. More representative data are available from several countries including Japan and South Korea. Several initiatives in Asia are improving the performance of health surveillance in wildlife and data sharing. These include initiatives supported by WOA and the Asian Society of Conservation Medicine (ASCM). WOA introduced the Wildlife Health Framework in 2020 to promote a One Health approach to maintaining wildlife health worldwide. This framework emphasises networking among government officials and researchers involved in wildlife health, including national focal points for wildlife and has led to networking initiatives in East Asia, South Asia, the Pacific, and Southeast Asia, primarily through regular online meetings. These meetings provide a platform for information sharing on various aspects of wildlife health and surveillance. Existing information-sharing platforms in Asia provide a strong foundation for improving data collection and analysis. Development of national surveillance programmes for HPAI in wildlife in all Asian countries would improve surveillance coverage of relevant populations. International exchanges and financial assistance programmes may be key to achieving this.

Addendum - HPAI in Russia, 2020 to 2024 (based on EFSA reports between August to December 2020 and September to December 2024, using data from reports by Russia to WOA, and the scientific literature)

Between August 2020 and September 2021, there were 20 HPAI H5 detections (4 H5NX, 5 H5N1, 11 H5N8) reported in wild birds in Russia. The majority of these were in waterfowl species. Available sequences of these viruses from wild birds from Russia between July 2020 and February 2021 belonged to clade 2.3.4.4b.

Table 2. Summary of reported detections of HPAI in wildlife in Asia 2020-2024 (Top: Number of occurrences, Middle: Subtype, Bottom: Main infected species).

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Total (year unknown)
Japan	7 H5N8 Accipitridae species, eastern buzzard, peregrine falcon, owl, hooded crane, mandarin duck	27 H5N8 eastern buzzard, mallard	177 H5N1, H5N2, H5Nx whooper swan, mute swan, large-billed crow, Ezo red fox, Ezo raccoon dog	140 H5N1, H5Nx, H5N6 large-billed crow, whooper swan, Eurasian wigeon, Ezo red fox	105 H5N1, H5N5, H5Nx large-billed crow	464 (8)
Republic of Korea	60 H5N8 whooper swan, mallard, mandarin duck	73 H5N8 whooper swan, mallard, great white egret	39 H5N1, H5N8 greater white-fronted goose	16 H5N1, H5N6 whooper swan	13 H5N1 H5N6 H5Nx mandarin duck	202 (1)
People's Republic of China	1 H5N8 mute swan	7 H5N8, H5N1 black swan, mandarin duck, grebe, mute swan, common shelduck, geese species	1 H5N8 unspecified species	2 H5N1 unspecified bird species	3 H5N1, H5Nx unspecified species, brown-headed gull	20 (6)
Chinese Taipei	2 H5Nx northern pintail	2 H5N1, H5N5 swan species, black-faced spoonbill	3 H5N1, H5N2 crested serpent eagle, Harris's hawk, whiskered tern, lesser sand plover, duck species	3 H5N1 whiskered tern, black-faced spoonbill	2 H5N1 black-faced spoonbill, grey heron	12 (0)
Nepal			1 H5N1 crow species	1 H5N1 crow species		2 (0)
India	2 H5N8 house crow	8 H5N1, H5N1, HPAIVx crow species, geese species, crane, unspecified birds		1 H5N1 black swan, Phasianid species		26 (15)
Cambodia				1 H5N1 unspecified species		1 (0)
Total no. occurrences	72	117	221	164	123	727

Between September 2021 and September 2022, there were 8 HPAI H5 detections (5 H5NX, 3 H5N1) reported in wild birds in Russia. The species were not indicated. Available sequences of wild birds from Russia between December 2021 and March 2022 belonged to clade 2.3.4.4b.

Between September 2022 and September 2023, there were 54 HPAI H5 detections (all H5N1) reported in wild birds in Russia. The highest number of reports (38) was in the period April to June 2023, and involved various species in the families Laridae and Alcidae, mainly in the western part of Russia. The second highest number of reports was in the period June to September 2023, and involved various species from the same two families, in both the western and in the far eastern part of Russia. These high numbers correspond to the peak seen in HPAI H5N1 detections in colony-breeding seabirds, particularly black-headed gulls, in the rest of Europe between April and September 2023 (see section on Europe). Genetic analysis indicates that the HPAI H5N1 viruses detected in wild birds from western Russia (Leningrad region) between June and September 2023 were introduced from Europe. In 2023, a mass mortality event among northern fur seals on Tyuleniy Island in the Sea of Okhotsk was linked to the highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) A(H5N1) virus, clade 2.3.4.4b. Over 3,500 seals and some Steller sea lions died between July and August [16, 17].

Between September 2023 and December 2024, there were no reports of HPAI H5 detections in wild birds or poultry in Russia.

Addendum – HPAI in Georgia, 2020-2022

Surveillance for HPAI and LPAI viruses in live wild birds in Georgia has been performed since 2010, recently funded in part through a European-wide funding mechanism (the EFSA-led SENTINEL Wild Birds project, <https://sentinelwildbirds.inu.se/>). For this surveillance, migratory waterfowl were sampled during autumn in the southern upland region, and both migratory waterfowl and gulls were sampled at the Black Sea coast in winter. In the period 2020 to 2022, a total of 6,841 samples were collected, in which 468 influenza viruses were detected, 99 of which were of the H5 subtype. These H5-positive samples were collected both in autumn and in winter from mallards and Eurasian teal. In 2020, some of the H5-positive samples were HPAI by genome sequencing, and none were LPAI. In 2021, all the H5-positive samples were LPAI. In 2022, two of the H5-positive samples were HPAI. Whole genome phylogenetic analyses of the viruses from Georgia showed that the HPAI H5 viruses in 2020 were ancestral for all gene segments to the viruses detected in the EU, and were identified 1–2 months before the closest genetically-related sequences were detected in Europe, Kuwait and Russia subsequently [18].

Middle East

For this analysis, the Middle East (Annex I) is defined as sixteen countries including those on the Arabian Peninsula (Kuwait, Qatar, the United Arab Emirates, Oman, Yemen, Saudi Arabia, and Bahrain), Israel, Palestine, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Iraq, Iran, Türkiye and Cyprus.

Introduction

This section describes the status of HPAI infection in wildlife in the Middle East from October 2020 to September 2024. From October 2020, only Israel, Iraq and Cyprus have reported clade 2.3.4.4b HPAI (H5N1) outbreaks in wild birds to WOAHP via the WAHIS. The first outbreak was reported in Israel in December 2021 and 37 outbreaks in wild birds were reported in the Middle East for the period of interest.

Middle Eastern countries host important stopover sites for birds migrating between Europe and Asia and Africa, and within Asia [19]. Marshes in southern Iraq form an important wetland and island groups and islets on the Arabian Peninsula provide breeding habitat for seabirds and

shorebirds [20]. Monitoring of these sites and bird populations and investigation of mortality events is important to understand all pressures on these populations.

Spread and impact

Three major migratory flyways cross the Middle East: Central Asia, East Asia/ East Africa and Black Sea/ Mediterranean [19]. Countries such as Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Oman, the United Arab Emirates, Iraq, Iran and Israel host stopover sites that likely place them at risk of HPAI introductions [21, 22]. Sequencing of viruses detected in Iran, from 2016-2018, from close to wetlands near the Caspian Sea, provided evidence of virus introductions from Asia and Europe and further dissemination from Iran to Egypt and Israel [23, 24]. Birds are known to stop over in this area during migration from Siberia and northern Russia [25].

There are few published descriptions of clade 2.3.4.4b H5N1 viruses detected in the Middle East, but there is further evidence of transmission routes from Asia and Europe. The haemagglutinin (HA) gene of the first H5N1 virus detected in Israel, in turkeys, was found to be identical to those from poultry and wild waterfowl in Russia and Italy [22]. Furthermore, Sheikh et al. [26] reported that the 2024 Iraqi gull virus' HA gene sequence was most closely related to viruses detected in Kazakhstan, which reported outbreaks in early 2024.

Figure 4. WAHIS reports Middle East region, including total of 37 reports of HPAI H5N1 in wild birds.

Epidemiological year 2021-22

In December 2021, Israel was the first Middle Eastern country to report outbreaks of clade 2.3.4.4b HPAI (H5N1), in wild birds, and the only country to report in the 2021-22 epidemiological year. The first outbreak involved the death of at least 10,000 common/Eurasian cranes, mostly in the Hula valley, and hundreds of great white pelicans. Approximately 40,000 cranes stop over on their way from Russia and Scandinavia to North and East Africa [22, 27, 28]. Nadler-Valency et al. [29] estimated a mortality rate of 20-27% in the Hula Valley but also report that many birds appeared to recover after four to five days. Artificial feeding, causing aggregation of cranes, may have contributed to virus spread and the high mortality [30, 31]. The cranes are fed to attract them away from agricultural operations such as fish farms. The feeding was halted and carcasses were collected, in an attempt to slow virus spread [22, 31]. The number of overwintering cranes has

declined since 2021 but was already decreasing in 2019-20 season and the rate of decline did not seem to increase after 2021. Other management practices, such as reduced feeding in 2019-20 and increased roosting site disturbance from 2019 to 2021, may have played a role [29].

Individual detections in six other species were reported to WOAHA from Israel in late 2021 to early 2022. The species comprised birds of prey and scavengers (Eurasian buzzard, hooded crow and common kestrel), and water birds (little egret, marbled teal, and common shelduck) [28]. However, the intake of raptor fledglings at the Agamon Wildlife Rehabilitation Centre dropped by 43% in 2022, compared to 2021 [29]. Additionally, a bioacoustics study in Agmon Hula Lake Park, conducted from November 2020 to October 2022 found a significant decrease in avian vocal activity from 2021 to 2022 [32]. The effect of the virus on other avian species may therefore have been significantly more than the observed mortalities.

Epidemiological year 2022-23

Israel and Cyprus reported only four HPAI detections to WAHIS in the 2022-23 epidemiological year. Three detections in wild waterfowl were reported from Israel from November 2022 to January 2023 [33]. Affected waterfowl species comprised northern shoveler and mallard, and a dunlin was reported from the Hula Valley. Cyprus reported an infected wild mallard in November 2022 [34].

Epidemiological year 2023-24

The 2023-24 period again saw mass mortality in cranes in Israel and gulls in Iraq and smaller numbers of other species reported from Israel and Cyprus. The outbreak in common cranes in Israel started in January 2024 and continued until at least March. Of the 10,000-15,000 cranes estimated to have overwintered [29, 35], 350 detections were reported on WAHIS [36]. Nadler-Valency et al. [29] estimate a mortality rate of 1.4-2.6% and report that clinical signs were milder than in 2021-22, limited to weakness. They postulate that this could be due to improved herd immunity after the 2021-22 outbreak but also highlight that the outbreak occurred later in the season, when conditions were less favourable for virus survival. Virus was not detected in water samples, in contrast to 2021-22, which may have also been influenced by water management that included increased outflow. In addition, water levels were raised to flood the main roosting site, which encouraged cranes to roost at smaller, more dispersed sites [29, 35]. There was pressure on government authorities to ensure collection of carcasses outside the nature reserves [35].

Israel reported small numbers of detections in ten other species in the 2023-24 year: Eurasian teal, marbled teal, grey heron, black stork, peregrine falcon, great white pelican, herring gull, black-headed gull and yellow-legged gull [36, 37], and Cyprus reported an infected peregrine falcon in February 2024 [38].

Iraq reported an outbreak of HPAI H5N1 in gulls from two islands on Dukan Lake (As-Sulaymaniyah province) in May 2024 [39]. This was the first outbreak of HPAI H5 reported by the country since 2016. Fifty detections were reported on WAHIS but media reports mentioned thousands of deaths. Videos show many carcasses and live birds with clinical signs including stupor, head twitches, and torticollis [40]. From the photographs in the manuscript by Sheikh et al. [26] and videos online, as well as the breeding species listed by Ararat [41], it seems likely that the gulls affected were slender-billed gulls.

There were additional media reports about an outbreak in gulls at Little Zap River, near Dukan Lake [42], HPAI detection in a gull in the Ain al-Faras area, Salah Al-Din Province [43, 44], and mortalities at Mosul Dam, Nineveh Province [45].

Surveillance and data quality

There appears to be limited publicly available information on the avian influenza surveillance programmes conducted in countries of the Middle East. The wildlife surveillance programme in Saudi Arabia comprises reporting of mass mortality events to the national animal health authority,

and surveys for dead birds in protected and rural areas [46]. A meeting supported by WOA, held in Jordan in December 2024, included a goal of strengthening national and regional surveillance and reporting systems for HPAI.

Development of national surveillance programmes for HPAI in wildlife in all Middle Eastern countries would improve surveillance coverage of relevant populations. International exchanges and financial assistance programmes may be key to achieving this.

Europe

Introduction

This section describes the status of HPAI infection in wildlife in Europe (Annex I) from October 2020 to October 2024. HPAI H5 virus was first detected in wild birds and poultry in Europe in 2005 [47]. Since then, HPAI H5 caused epidemics in wild birds in Europe mainly in autumn and winter, linked to autumn migration of wild waterfowl, and then apparently disappeared in spring and summer. Since 2020-2021, there have been HPAI epidemics in wild birds every year, with spillover to poultry, captive birds and wild, farmed, captive and domestic mammals. In both wild birds and poultry, the HPAI epidemics in the years 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023 were the three largest in European history [48].

Spread and impact

Epidemiological year 2020-2021

Between 1 October 2020 and 30 September 2021, there were 2,406 HPAI detections in wild birds from 29 countries in Europe [49-52]. There were two peaks of detections, a small one between October and December 2020 and a large one between February and May 2021 (Figure 5). Each epidemic involved mainly waterfowl, with smaller numbers of raptors. HPAI detections in wild birds were widespread across Europe, and were concentrated in Denmark, the Netherlands, and north Germany (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in Europe by week of suspicion (the week when an HPAI case is first suspected; dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2020-2021 from 5 October 2020 to 4 October 2021. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 2,407. Data source: EFSA

Figure 6. Map of Europe showing locations and categories of wild birds in which HPAI was detected in epidemiological year 2020-2021. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 2,407.

Notable aspects of this epidemiological year include:

1. It was the first time that such high mortalities of barnacle geese and red knots were observed, species which had not been reported as affected before. A total of 3,435 barnacle geese were found dead in the Netherlands alone, representing up to 4.8% of the Dutch non-breeding population of barnacle geese [53]. A total of 3,500 red knots, all belonging to the subspecies *islandica*, were found dead in December 2020 in a localised die-off in Germany, representing about 1% of the entire flyway population of *islandica* red knots [54].
2. It was the first time that such high wild bird mortality associated with HPAI H5 was observed in spring. This implied a temporal overlap with spring migration. Spring migration of anseriform or charadriiform birds was inferred to be a possible source of HPAI H5 virus detected in a white-tailed eagle found dead in Iceland in October 2021 [55]. It also implied a temporal overlap with the breeding season. Mortality of nestlings of white-tailed eagles from HPAI H5 was recorded in Germany in May 2021 [56], and there was a HPAI H5-associated die-off of more than 10% of the 1,500 great skuas breeding off the U.K. coast in July 2021 [57].
3. Virus detections in wild birds continued throughout summer for the first time [58]. The observed persistence of virus circulation in wild birds in Europe was supported by phylogenetic analysis of viruses detected in 2020-2021 [59].

Phylogenetic analysis showed that the H5N8 EA-2020-A genotype [60] predominated in Europe until July 2021, when the H5N1 EA-2020-C genotype became more frequently detected (Figure 7). Except for one H5N8 genotype that emerged in July in central Russia, all genotypes detected were reassortants between that H5N8 genotype and LPAI viruses circulating in Europe and Asia.

Figure 7. Overview of key genotypes of HPAI H5 detected in wild birds in EU/EAA between September 2020 and November 2024, based on complete genome sequencing of part of the HPAI H5 viruses obtained by the surveillance reported here.

Epidemiological year 2021-2022

Between 1 October 2021 and 30 September 2022, there were 3,898 HPAI detections in wild birds from 34 countries in Europe [61-64]. There were four peaks. The first two (between October and December 2021, and between December 2021 and May 2022) involved mainly waterfowl, while the second two (between May and August 2022, and between August and September 2022) involved mainly colony-breeding seabirds and raptors (Figure 8). HPAI detections in wild birds were widely distributed across Europe, with a concentration in a band from the Baltic Sea coasts of southern Sweden, Germany and Denmark in the east, to the North and Wadden Sea coasts of Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands in the west from October 2021 to May 2022, and a concentration of detections along the western coasts of Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, France and Spain from May to September 2022 (Figure 9).

Notable aspects of this epidemiological year include:

1. It was the first time that multiple species of colony-breeding seabirds were involved in such high numbers. HPAI H5N1 virus infection was associated with unusually high mortality at 35 colonies of northern gannets. At Bass Rock in Scotland, the world's largest northern gannet colony, the number of occupied nest sites decreased by at least 71%, breeding success declined by about 66%, and the apparent adult survival between 2021 and 2022 (77%) was estimated to be substantially lower than the 10-year average (94%) [65]. HPAI H5N1 virus infection was associated with 20,531 adult sandwich terns found dead at breeding sites throughout north-western Europe within two months of the first reported mortalities, representing more than 17% of the total north-western European breeding population [66]. In great skuas, HPAI H5N1 virus infection was associated with more than 2,600 adult birds found dead across the U.K. by September 2022: 13% of the UK population and 8% of the world population [67]. In Dalmatian pelicans, HPAI H5N1 virus infection was associated with 2,566 adults found dead at breeding colonies in Greece, Albania, Montenegro and Romania. This represents a mortality of more than 40% of the south-east European population, and about 10% of the global population [68].

Figure 8: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in Europe by week of suspicion (the week when an HPAI case is first suspected; dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2021-2022 from 4 October 2021 to 2 October 2022. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 3,901. Data source: EFSA

Figure 9. Map of Europe showing locations and categories of wild birds in which HPAI was detected in epidemiological year 2021-2022. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 3,901.

2. The third and fourth peaks in 2021-2022 involved increased number of raptors, in particular peregrine falcons, Eurasian buzzards and white-tailed eagles. In the Netherlands, 28 peregrine falcons were found dead, representing up to 56% of the Dutch wintering population of peregrine falcons; as well as 363 Eurasian buzzards, representing up to 12.1% of the wintering population of Eurasian buzzards [69]. On two islands off the U.K. coast, declines of breeding success of white-tailed eagles (from 66% in 2021 to 24% in 2022) and golden eagles (from 55% in 2021 to 16% in 2022) were attributed to HPAI [70].

Phylogenetic analysis showed the H5N1 EA-2020-C genotype was dominant in Europe early in the 2021-2022 epidemiological year (Figure 7). In February 2022, the H5N1 EA-2021-AB genotype became predominant. These two genotypes were mainly detected among wild waterfowl. In May 2022, a new genotype originating from reassortment event between genotype EA-2021-AB and H13 LPAI viruses, a subtype primarily found in gulls, emerged. This genotype, EA-2022-BB, was associated with the two peaks in colony-breeding seabirds in spring-summer.

Epidemiological year 2022-2023

Between 1 October 2022 and 30 September 2023, there were 4,200 HPAI detections in wild birds from 30 countries in Europe [71-75]. There were three peaks. The first peak (October to December 2022) involved mainly waterfowl, while the second (December 2022 to April 2023) and third peaks (April to September 2023) involved mainly colony-breeding seabirds (Figure 10). HPAI detections in wild birds were widely distributed across Europe, with a concentration in countries and regions bordering the North Sea: Denmark, northwest Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium and the U.K., as well as northern Italy (Figure 11).

This epidemiological year was different in two aspects:

1. It was the first time that black-headed gulls in breeding colony sites across Europe had died from HPAI H5 (and specifically, EA-2022-BB) in such large numbers. The second peak coincided with wintering, spring migration, pre-breeding aggregation and occupation of breeding sites by black-headed gulls [76]. During this second peak, there were reports of mass mortalities of tens to thousands of adult black-headed gulls per event in Italy, France, Belgium, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Czechia, Germany, Poland, the U.K. and Sweden. The third peak coincided with the breeding period and departure of adults and juveniles from breeding sites. During this third peak, mortalities of tens to thousands of both juvenile and adult black-headed gulls per event were reported from the Netherlands, Belgium, the U.K., Sweden, and Finland.
2. It also was the first time that several other species of the family Laridae (gulls) had died in such high numbers from HPAI H5, again caused by genotype EA-2022-BB. HPAI-H5-associated mortality of tens to thousands of individuals per breeding site were reported for common terns in the U.K., Spain and the Netherlands; gull-billed terns in Spain; sandwich terns in Spain, Italy, Belgium and the Netherlands; Mediterranean gulls in the Netherlands; and black-legged kittiwakes in Norway. A decline of more than 50% (from 19,000 to 9,000) in the estimated number of breeding pairs of sandwich terns in the Netherlands and the Flemish part of Belgium in 2023 was attributed to HPAI H5N1.

About 95% of the genetically characterised HPAI H5N1 viruses collected between October 2022 and September 2023 belonged to three genotypes (Figure 7). Between October 2022 and January 2023, the EA-2021-AB genotype dominated. From February 2023, the EA-2022-BB genotype became the most frequently identified variant, mainly in Laridae and especially black-headed gulls. Of note is the incursion of this genotype into a fur farm in Spain in October 2022 [77], and into fur farms in Finland in July 2023 [78]. Also of note is that EA-2022-BB viruses from wild birds along the Mediterranean coast in April-June 2023 clustered with viruses from wild birds in West Africa, suggesting that virus incursion may have occurred through spring migration from Africa to Europe. The EA-2022-CH genotype was identified for the first time in October 2022 and circulated in wild birds mainly in Eastern Europe.

Figure 10: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in Europe by week of suspicion (the week when an HPAI case is first suspected; dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2022-2023 from 3 October 2022 to 1 October 2023. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 4,205. Data source: EFSA

Figure 11. Map of Europe showing locations and categories of wild birds in which HPAI was detected in epidemiological year 2022-2023. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 4,205.

Epidemiological year 2023-2024

Between 1 October 2023 and 30 September 2024, there were 725 HPAI detections in wild birds from 30 countries in Europe [48, 71, 79, 80]. There were three small peaks: the first peak (between October and December 2023) involved mainly the category 'other bird species'; the second peak (between December 2023 and April 2024) involved mainly waterfowl; and the third peak (between June and September 2024) involved mainly colony-breeding seabirds (Figure 12). HPAI detections in wild birds were widely distributed across Europe, with concentrations in Denmark, northwest Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium and Romania (Figure 13).

The most different aspect of this epidemiological year was the high mortality of common cranes in November 2023 in Hungary, where there is a key stopover site in their autumn migration route [81]. Up to 6 December 2023, 20 to 30 thousand common cranes were estimated to have died in Hungary.

The relatively high number of HPAI detections in mute swans and whooper swans in the second peak was associated with a HPAI-H5-associated mortality of swans in Moldova and the adjacent part of Romania, where 261 swans were found dead in December 2023 to January 2024 [82].

More than 90% of the genetically characterised HPAI viruses collected since October 2023 belonged to seven different A(H5N1) genotypes and one A(H5N5) genotype (Figure 3). All the viruses obtained from common cranes belonged to the H5N1 EA-2023-DA genotype, while the H5N1 genotype EA-2024-DI was circulating among Anseriformes in Eastern Europe between the end of December 2023 and March 2024. All the characterized viruses from Laridae and Sulidae (gannets and boobies) in the Iberian Peninsula belonged to the EA-2022-BB and EA-2023-DT genotypes. The EA-2023-DT genotype evolved from the EA-2022-BB genotype by further reassortment with a gull-adapted H13 LPAI virus. Since May 2024, it apparently replaced the EA-2022-BB genotype in this geographic area. The EA-2021-I genotype, the only one of subtype H5N5, emerged in Russia in 2020 and has been circulating in Europe since the 2020-2021 epidemiological year. During the 2023-24 this genotype was detected mainly in seabirds and raptors in northern Europe. Of note, all the viruses of this genotype characterised at the beginning of 2024 contained an important marker of virus adaptation to mammals (PB2-E627K) in the PB2 protein, suggesting a spread in the wild bird population of a virus with a possible increased zoonotic potential.

Figure 12: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in Europe by week of suspicion (the week when an HPAI case is first suspected; dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2023-2024 from 2 October 2023 to 6 October 2024. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 785. Data source: EFSA

Figure 13. Map of Europe showing locations and categories of wild birds in which HPAI was detected in epidemiological year 2023-2024. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reported detections is 785.

HPAI H5 in wild mammals

Over these four years, HPAI H5 infected several species of wild mammals in Europe, mostly detected in individual animals rather than mass mortalities. The species in which HPAI H5 was detected were: red fox, Eurasian lynx, European polecat, European badger, pine marten, beech marten, Eurasian otter, raccoon, harbour seal, grey seal, northern fur seal, walrus, harbour porpoise, and common dolphin.

Surveillance and data quality

Surveillance for HPAI in wildlife in Europe is based mainly on HPAI surveillance in wild birds by individual European countries in response to EU legislation requiring member states to carry out surveillance programmes in poultry and wild birds [83]. This surveillance consists of sampling wild birds that have been found dead, found injured or sick, or hunted with clinical signs. When HPAI has been detected in wild birds, this surveillance may be increased by intensified detection and collection of dead and sick birds. The resulting data are collated and reported every year by EFSA, comprising results from EU/EEA countries and others in and bordering Europe [75]. Although surveillance is country-wide and involves all wild bird species in principle, there is an emphasis on a target list of bird species [84] and particular habitats e.g. wetlands and agricultural land. There is less emphasis on surveillance in wild mammals, which was not obligatory until 2023-2024.

There are potential biases in the data related to temporal and geographical variation in observer effort, and related to the overall surveillance goal to provide an early warning for the poultry sector.

For example, dead birds are more likely to be found and reported during months when people spend more time outdoors, and in geographical areas that are more densely populated. Surveillance efforts are more likely to prioritise investigation of suspect detections in new locations over confirmation of the number of birds affected in an ongoing event. It is likely also that smaller and more cryptic species are less easily found by surveillance and are thus under-represented in the data. Broadening the goals of surveillance for HPAI in wildlife in Europe to protect the health of wildlife as well as that of domestic animals and humans, would bring the goals of this surveillance in line with the One Health approach [85].

Africa

Introduction

This section describes the status of HPAI infection in wildlife in Africa (Annex I) from October 2020 to October 2024. HPAI Gs/GD-lineage H5 virus was first reported from Africa in Zimbabwe and Nigeria in January 2006 [47, 86]. HPAI Gs-Gd-lineage H5N1 outbreaks were reported to WOA from West Africa, Egypt, Libya, Sudan, Republic of South Sudan and Djibouti over the following years until 2016. The first Gs/GD-lineage virus to be reported from the southern half of Africa was clade 2.3.4.4 H5N8 in 2017.

How these HPAI viruses were introduced and spread in Africa is still unclear. However, movements of migratory ducks and shorebirds (suborder Charadrii) may have been responsible, given that they are hosts of LPAI viruses. Gaidet et al. [87] found LPAI viruses in Palearctic migratory duck species in West Africa: garganey, northern pintail, Eurasian teal, and northern shoveler. Gaidet et al. [87] also found LPAI viruses in Eurasian shorebirds including curlew sandpiper, ruff and spotted redshank in Mali (West Africa) and Tunisia (North Africa). However, Palearctic migratory ducks and Eurasian shorebirds are unlikely to have been responsible for onward spread of HPAI from West Africa to southern Africa. Curlew sandpipers and ruffs do overwinter as far south as southern Africa, but migrate via East Africa [88] so seem unlikely to spread viruses present in West Africa. Also, they arrive in the austral spring (September to November) whereas HPAI appeared to be introduced to southern Africa in the austral autumn (March to May). As for Palearctic migratory duck species, they do not occur naturally in southern Africa [88].

Rather, the onward spread of HPAI from West Africa to southern Africa is hypothesised to have been via relay-transmission involving intra-African nomadic duck species [89]. Some southern African duck species may move considerable distances within the African continent [90]. For example, Gaidet et al. [91] showed that a white-faced whistling duck travelled 655 km over 47 days, while infected with HPAI virus. While strong seasonal patterns in the northern hemisphere drive waterfowl movements and hence peaks of AIV infection, intra-African waterfowl movements are relatively unpredictable [92, 93]. They respond to more short-term and less predictable climatic factors such as rainfall [94].

Spread and impact

Epidemiological year 2020-2021

Between 1 October 2020 and 30 September 2021, HPAI H5N1 was reported in wild birds in both West Africa and southern Africa. The first HPAI H5 outbreaks in wild birds in Africa were reported in January 2021 from Senegal and Mauritania (West Africa), involving great white pelicans in the delta of the Senegal River. It was estimated that 3000 pelicans died, mainly juveniles, comprising 8.4% of the Senegalese colony [95, 96]. The viruses recovered from chickens and a great white pelican in Senegal were closely related to viruses detected in Europe from October to December 2020 and were hypothesised to have been introduced from southern Europe via migratory birds [96].

HPAI H5N1 virus detections in wild birds were reported in South Africa and Botswana (southern Africa) between April and September 2021. Approximately 130 confirmed or suspected wild bird detections were made in South Africa in that period (Figure 14).

About 60 comprised great white pelicans that died between May and July, with smaller numbers of other colony-breeding seabirds, including Cape cormorants, Hartlaub's gulls and Kelp gulls [97] (Roberts, in preparation). Waterfowl species were represented by Egyptian geese, a spur-winged goose and a yellow-billed duck. Other infected species included hadada ibis, sacred ibis, African fish eagle and blue crane (WAHIS Event 3733). These viruses from South Africa were most closely related to viruses detected in Senegal and were genetically distinguishable from those detected in Europe and Asia. Thirteen sub-genotypes (SA1-SA13) had been detected by the end of September, indicating multiple introductions [97]. HPAI H5N1 virus was detected in Botswana between June and September 2021, in mourning collared doves and an African fish eagle. The wild bird detections were dead birds found in poorly accessible areas, so there may have been other unobserved mortality events. The viruses from birds in Botswana formed a distinct sub-clade when compared to other African and European viruses [98].

Figure 14. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in African countries that regularly reported (Republic of South Africa) by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2020-2021. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reports 103. Data source: WAHIS.

Epidemiological year 2021-2022

Between 1 October 2021 and 30 September 2022, H5N1 HPAI again was reported in wild birds in southern Africa (Figure 15) and West Africa. HPAI H5 was detected in Cape cormorants in southern Africa in association with mortality of 24,000 individuals between October and December 2021 in South Africa (Roberts, in preparation), and mortality of more than 8,000 individuals between December 2021 and February 2022 in neighbouring Namibia [99]. Based on an estimated 57,400 breeding pairs [100], at least 8% of the Cape cormorant breeding population in Namibia could have been lost. In South Africa, HPAI H5 also was detected in African penguins, with nearly 300 mortalities recorded, mostly in late 2021 but with a smaller peak in July–September 2022. HPAI H5 also was recorded in other colony-breeding seabird species, with the peak in mortality from October 2021 to January 2022. A seabird-restricted virus sub-lineage (SA13) that had been detected from September 2021 persisted throughout 2022, longer than all other South African sub-lineages [97] (Roberts, in preparation). Other affected species in which HPAI H5 was detected included were African sacred ibises on a seabird breeding island in October 2021 and white storks in February 2022 [101].

In West Africa, another HPAI H5 outbreak was reported in great white pelican juveniles (1,016/11,563; mortality rate 7.7%) in January 2022 in Senegal, which was of similar magnitude to 2021 [102]. Beyit et al. [95] reported the deaths of 58 adult great white pelicans in Mauritania in February and that viruses identified were most closely related to some found in Europe in 2022. This suggests a new virus introduction.

In Nigeria in March and April 2022, HPAI H5 was detected in 25 of 226 apparently healthy, live wild birds tested in the Hadeji-Nguru wetland [103]. The wetland hosts Palearctic and Afrotropical migrant water birds, along with resident wild birds and domestic waterfowl. All species with more than 10 birds sampled at a site had at least one positive, so sample size may have influenced the species in which detections were made. Infections were detected in resident white-faced whistling ducks, square-tailed nightjars, African jacanas, spur-winged geese, Palearctic migrant ruffs, and white storks. The genetic sequences of these viruses did not align with those detected in Nigerian poultry since 2021, suggesting a new introduction of HPAI to Nigeria.

Figure 15. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in African countries that regularly reported (Republic of South Africa) by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological years 2021-2022. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reports 47. Data source: WAHIS.

Epidemiological year 2022-2023

Between 1 October 2022 and 30 September 2023, HPAI H5 was reported again in wild birds in southern Africa (Figure 16) and West Africa. In South Africa HPAI H5 was detected in association with mortality of colony-breeding seabirds, mainly 34 African penguins. Of 28 clade 2.3.4.4b viruses detected in seabirds between March and July 2023, 25 belonged to the seabird SA13 sub-genotype. Most mortalities observed were in greater crested terns, with 82 cases counted, though the virus was detected in other species [104] (Roberts, in preparation). Between February and November, 477 environmental faecal samples, of which 25% tested positive for HPAI H5 virus, were collected from wild ducks in six of nine provinces of South Africa. Virus prevalence was especially high between February and July 2023. In April 2023 in South Africa, a wave of poultry outbreaks occurred from a newly introduced genotype (SA15), which was related to viruses detected in Botswana in 2021. Around the same time of the poultry outbreaks, the same sub-clade was detected in a sick Egyptian goose, a Hartlaub’s gull and two kelp gulls in South Africa [97, 104]. In July 2023 in South Africa, HPAI H5 detection was associated with the deaths of 40 grey-crowned cranes and a pied crow, reported from one location [105].

In Senegal, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau and Guinea (West Africa) between February and August 2023, HPAI H5 detection was associated with the mortality of over 25,000 colony-breeding seabirds. In The Gambia and Senegal, the peak of the outbreak occurred in April, with mortality of

West African crested terns (>10,000) and Caspian terns (4,600), with smaller numbers of sandwich terns, grey-headed gulls, great cormorants and 27 other species [73, 74, 106]. Jatta et al. [107] monitored seven sites in The Gambia and Senegal from October 2022 to September 2023 and detected small numbers of sick and dead birds in October 2022 but “negligible occurrences” between October 2022 and March 2023.

Figure 16. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in African countries that regularly reported (Republic of South Africa) by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2022-2023. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reports 57. Data source: WAHIS.

Epidemiological year 2023-24

Between 1 October 2023 and 30 September 2024, reports of HPAI H5 in wild birds were limited to a few detections in South Africa (Figure 17). Isolated detections of the seabird SA13 genotype were detected there in two greater crested terns in February and April 2024 [105] (Abolnik, pers. comm.).

Figure 17. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in African countries that regularly reported (Republic of South Africa) by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2023-2024. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reports 2. Data source: WAHIS.

Surveillance and data quality

Detections of HPAI in African wildlife have been largely via opportunistic sampling of sick and dead birds. In an OFFLU-led survey by Pavade and colleagues [108] published in 2010, avian influenza surveillance in wild birds was only reported from South Africa and Zimbabwe among African countries.

In recent years, avian influenza surveys in wild birds have been reported in the literature from southern Africa: Botswana [98], South Africa [97, 104], and Zambia [109]; West Africa: Nigeria [103]; and East Africa: Kenya [110]. It is striking that no HPAI detections have been reported from East Africa during the time period of this study.

Government funding for avian influenza surveillance in wild birds is very limited, which may contribute to under-detection. Avian influenza surveillance in wild birds described in the scientific literature since 2020 has largely been based on international or non-government funding. For example, Kalonda and colleagues [109] were supported by a World Bank-funded project on infectious diseases and by sources in Japan, and Munyua and colleagues [110] by U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention under the research cooperative agreement with Washington State University. Additionally, the FAO Emergency Centre for Transboundary Animal Disease Control (ECTAD) regional offices in Eastern and Southern Africa fund laboratory consumables for surveillance in Ethiopia, Kenya, the United Republic of Tanzania and Uganda through a USAID funded Global Health Security programme [111]. Avian influenza surveillance in wild birds in South Africa is currently mainly funded through the University of Pretoria, by a National Department of Science and Innovation and National Research Foundation grant and National Department of Trade and Industry grants, with contributions from provincial governments and poultry companies [97, 104]. Most of these surveillance projects have limited lifespans, so a more sustainable model is needed to build and maintain effective HPAI surveillance in wild birds in Africa. Development of national surveillance programmes for HPAI in wildlife in all African countries would improve surveillance coverage of relevant populations. International exchanges and financial assistance programmes may be key to achieving this.

North America

Introduction

This section describes the status of HPAI infection in wildlife in North America (Annex I) from November 2021 to October 2024. North America, comprising Canada, the United States (US), and Mexico, supports four major north-south migratory flyways (Atlantic, Mississippi, Central, and Pacific respectively, from east to west). Overlap of individuals and species within and among the flyways facilitate the movement of avian influenza viruses (AIVs) across the continent. Prior to 2014, HPAI detections in North America were sporadic and limited to poultry outbreaks [112]. However, the introduction of HPAI H5N8 clade 2.3.4.4 in 2014, likely via East Asia to Alaska, marked the first detection of HPAI in wild birds on the continent. By late 2016, HPAI was considered absent from North America, though related clade 2.3.4.4 viruses persisted in domestic and wild birds in Europe, Africa, and Asia [113].

The outbreak of HPAI H5 clade 2.3.4.4b viruses spread to North America in the autumn of 2021 by wild birds through Iceland, Greenland, Arctic, or pelagic migration routes with the earliest confirmed case detected in a great black-backed gull in eastern Canada in November 2021 [114, 115]. These viruses underwent extensive reassortment with LPAI viruses circulating in the region as they spread across North America in 2022, leading to the emergence of diverse viral genotypes by the spring [115]. Since then, multiple independent incursions of Eurasian HPAI H5 viruses have been documented along the Atlantic and Pacific coasts, leading to additional reassortments that have spread throughout and between flyways, and with new introductions continuing into 2024 [116].

Spread and impacts

Epidemiological year 2021-2022

The 2021-22 epidemiological year was characterized by a high number of detections of HPAI H5 in waterfowl, particularly during autumn and spring migration periods (Figure 18 and 19). Mortality events were prominent in sea ducks and geese, whereas dabbling ducks exhibited relatively high infection prevalence with minimal associated mortality.

Outbreaks and mortality in colony-breeding seabirds occurred during their breeding season. HPAI H5 was detected in 114 species of wild birds across 28 taxonomic families and 14 orders, and 16 species of wild mammals across 10 taxonomic families and 3 orders in Canada and the US.

Figure 18: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus morbidity/mortality surveillance detections in wild birds reported in North America by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological years 2021-2022. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. For ease, colony-breeding seabirds were defined differently from other continental regions in this report (Box), and include all species from the taxonomic order Charadriiformes, Pelecaniformes, Procellariiformes, Suliformes. Total reports 3,912. See section ‘Surveillance & data quality’ for data sources.

HPAI H5 appeared to affect waterfowl species differently, with mortality occurring at varying levels across groups. Diving and sea ducks, such as lesser scaup and American common eider, experienced large-scale mortality events, particularly at breeding colonies e.g., [117]. In contrast, HPAI H5 detections in dabbling ducks were relatively rare through surveillance of sick, dead or injured birds (morbidity and mortality investigations; often called ‘passive’ surveillance), but much more frequent via surveillance of apparently healthy live-captured and harvested birds (often called ‘active’ surveillance). Together, these findings suggest that dabbling ducks experienced relatively low levels of detectable morbidity and mortality despite high infection prevalence. For example, results from surveillance of apparently healthy dabbling ducks in Canada during this time period indicate an ~8% prevalence, while surveillance detected HPAI H5 in only 51 ducks found sick or dead. The highest number of detections through surveillance of birds found sick or dead were in mallard and wood duck with 16 and 10 individuals, respectively. In contrast, goose species exhibited widespread mortality despite relatively few detections in live or hunted individuals. In Canada, over 300 geese found sick or dead tested positive, with some of these detections associated with individuals collected as only a subsample of a mortality event. Geese made up >20% of all HPAI H5 detections in sick or dead birds between November 2021 - September 2022 [115].

Figure 19. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections in wild birds reported in North America based on birds sampled alive, through banding and hunter-harvested programmes, per wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2021-2022. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Colony-breeding seabirds were defined differently from other continental regions (Box), and include all species from the taxonomic order Charadriiformes, Pelecaniformes, Procellariiformes, Suliformes. Total reports 1,863. See section ‘Surveillance & data quality’ for data sources.

Over the 21-22 epidemiological year, surveillance in apparently healthy birds in Canada documented infection peaks occurring in spring and autumn. The highest prevalence occurred in American black duck, northern pintail, and mallard [115].

These findings highlight differences among waterfowl species during the first epidemiological year following the introduction of HPAI H5: while dabbling ducks were frequently infected with limited apparent mortality, geese and sea ducks appeared more susceptible to severe disease and mortality.

Mortality in raptors was detected throughout the year, with spatial and temporal patterns varying across the continent. Apparent regional clustering of raptor mortality suggests differences in exposure risk linked to diet, prey availability, and environmental persistence of the virus. Consumption of HPAI H5-infected animals and carcasses likely served as a primary mode of transmission to predatory and scavenging raptors. Mortality trends in these species may have been influenced by seasonal and geographical fluctuations in HPAI-associated mortality in other wildlife, as well as by exposure to infected material near poultry premises. Reported mortality in raptors occurred throughout the year and included species of eagles, hawks, falcons, owls and vultures and generally was widespread and persistent rather than occurring as discrete large-scale events, likely due to the solitary nature or low spatial density of individuals of these species. An exception to this pattern was observed in black vultures in which a mortality event occurred involving over 5,000 individuals [118].

HPAI H5 detections in seabirds in the US and Canada reported on government dashboards were relatively low during the winter (January–February 2022), accounting for only 4.1% of all detections (Figure 18), with nearly all detections occurring in the Atlantic Flyway (Figure 20). In the spring, detections remained low (8.7% of all detections) but were recorded across all flyways, with 57.3% occurring in the Atlantic Flyway, 27.0% in the Mississippi Flyway, 9.5% in the Central Flyway, and 6.2% in the Pacific Flyway (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Seasonal Trends in HPAI H5 Detections by Flyway in North America (2021–2024). Monthly detections of HP H5NX in the United States and Canada are shown across three epidemiological years (2021-2022 to 2023-2024), separated by major flyways (Atlantic, Mississippi, Central, and Pacific). Detections generally peak in autumn and early winter, with geographic shifts in intensity varying by year. The Central and Mississippi flyways show higher detections in spring, coinciding with waterfowl migration, while summer detections remain low across all flyways except during notable mortality events. See section ‘Surveillance & data quality’ for data sources. Map showing the waterfowl flyways copied from: Migratory bird flyways in North America., North Dakota Game and Fish Department, Public Domain, <https://www.fws.gov/media/migratory-bird-flyways-north-america>.

By summer, seabird detections in the US and Canada reported on government dashboards, increased markedly, rising to 29% of all reported detections. The Atlantic Flyway accounted for 64.2% of detections, with detections distributed more evenly across the remaining flyways (ranging from 10% to 15%). This increase in detections coincided with the breeding season, when colony-breeding seabirds aggregate in high densities likely facilitating transmission.

A mass mortality event was documented during the 2022 seabird breeding season (May - October). The mortality event began in May and persisted into early autumn, predominantly in eastern Canada (Quebec, Newfoundland and Labrador, Prince Edward Island, Nova Scotia, and New Brunswick) and, to a lesser extent, the northeastern United States. A concerted effort to collate reports of sick and dead wild birds in eastern Canada produced 40,391 HPAI-attributable mortalities after correcting for potential double counts [117].

Within these data, 26,193 northern gannets, 8,133 common murrelets and 2,326 gulls were recorded. During this period, outbreaks were documented at five of six North American northern gannet colonies, which together hosted 13% of the global population prior to 2022. Documented

adult gannet mortalities alone represent 11.5% of the North American breeding population [117], and aerial surveys in 2023 revealed a 39.8% decline in breeding northern gannets across all colonies (J.-F. Rail and S. I. Wilhelm pers comm. 2023), confirming substantial population level impacts. Increased numbers of immature northern gannets at one colony suggest potential compensatory recruitment [119], but overall losses remain high as of 2024, with the total number of breeding pairs observed at the six Canadian colonies remaining 35.3% below pre-HPAI numbers (J.-F. Rail and S. I. Wilhelm pers comm. 2024).

While mortality events in North Atlantic seabirds were concentrated at breeding sites, mortalities extended beyond the colonies as infected individuals dispersed. Some affected species, such as common murre and northern gannets, experienced prolonged mortality into late summer and autumn due to delayed nesting and chick-rearing, leading to continued virus circulation in the population.

Mortality events attributed to HPAI H5 outside of North Atlantic populations occurred concurrently in Central Flyway populations. At least 679 double-crested cormorants were included in morbidity and mortality reporting at inland colonies in Alberta, Canada during the 2022 breeding season (May - July). Estimated mortality represented 3-5% of local breeding populations at six lakes surveyed in mid-June (Government of Alberta, 2022). By autumn, detections in seabirds dropped sharply to 3.1% of all detections (Figures 18, 19, 21).

Figure 21. Seasonal Trends in HPAI H5 Detections by Species Group in North America (2021–2024).

Monthly detections of HP H5NX in the United States and Canada are shown across three epidemiological years (2021-2022 to 2023-2024), separated by species group. Each panel displays seasonal trends for waterfowl, raptors, seabirds, other birds. Waterfowl consistently drive autumn detections, while raptor and seabird detections peak in spring and summer during mortality events. See section 'Surveillance & data quality' for data sources.

HPAI H5 detections were recorded in multiple avian groups beyond waterfowl, raptors, and colony-breeding seabirds. Affected groups included species associated with aquatic habitats, such as shorebirds, grebes and waders (e.g. egrets and herons); scavenging passerines, primarily American crow, common raven, black-billed magpie, and blue jay; and peri-domestic passerines and Columbiformes sampled on HPAI H5-infected poultry farms. Infections detected in scavenging passerines were likely associated with consumption of infected wild bird carcasses, whereas phylogenetic analyses suggest that detections in peri-domestic species largely resulted from spillover from infected poultry [120]. The presence of HPAI H5 in passerine species underscores the potential for spillover into diverse ecological niches, including urban and agricultural environments.

HPAI H5 mortality was documented in a variety of wild mammal species throughout their range in North America during the first epidemiological year. Most detections occurred in terrestrial carnivores, primarily raccoon, striped skunk and red fox, with occasional detections in other scavenging and predatory mammals. HPAI-associated mortality was also confirmed in all three North American bear species, though detections were infrequent [121].

Terrestrial mammal detections in the US and Canada reported on government dashboards, first occurred in spring. The number of detections remained low but persistent through summer.

HPAI H5 mortality in marine mammals in North America was first detected in a single bottlenose dolphin in Florida, US in March 2022 [122]. Soon after, a larger mortality event was observed in harbour seals and grey seals further up the Atlantic coast, impacting an estimated 500 seals in the St. Lawrence Estuary and Gulf of Maine between the months of May and July 2022 in what was likely separate but parallel spillover events from sympatric gulls, terns, and eiders [123, 124].

Compared to avian species, the overall number of detections in wild mammals remained low, suggesting that while transmission was occurring, spillover into mammals was more limited and/or less frequently detected. However, the seasonal detection pattern, particularly in terrestrial carnivores, aligns with peak avian mortality events, indicating a temporal link between scavenging behaviours and infection risk.

Wholly Eurasian lineage viruses (genotypes A1 and A2) were first detected in Atlantic Canada and the east coast of the US in the winter of 2021 (Figure 22). These viruses spread southward through the Atlantic Flyway until the spring of 2022, when they were carried north along the Atlantic, Mississippi and Central flyways [125]. Concurrently, an entirely Eurasian lineage virus (genotype A3) was inferred to be introduced from East Asia to North America via Alaska, US in late 2021, though it was not detected until spring 2022 [126]. The spring of 2022 also marked the emergence of diverse HPAI H5N1 reassortant viruses that were the progeny of Eurasian-lineage H5N1 viruses and North American lineage LPAI viruses. While wholly Eurasian lineage viruses continued to circulate in the Atlantic Flyway through the spring and summer of 2022, they were largely replaced by reassortant viruses in the Mississippi, Central and Pacific flyways over this period. The reassortant genotype B2.1 replaced Eurasian lineage viruses in the Mississippi and Central flyways, which was itself replaced by genotype B3.2 by the autumn of 2022 [125]. Genotype B3.2 was detected in the Pacific flyway over this time period, particularly in Alaska, US, but detections throughout this flyway were predominately genotype B4.1 (Figure 22). An additional wholly Eurasian lineage viral genotype (A4) was purportedly introduced from East Asia into North America via Alaska in late summer 2022 [126].

Figure 22. Distribution of H5Nx HPAI genotypes in North America over three epidemiological years. Metadata for all clade 2.3.4.4b viruses collected from wildlife hosts in Canada, the United States, and Mexico between October 1, 2021 and September 30, 2024 were retrieved from the Global Initiative for Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID). Viruses with incomplete date, location, or genotype metadata were removed from the data set, leaving a total of 10,047 viruses. Maps (top panel) summarize the relative proportion and distribution of genotypes across discrete geographic regions for each epidemiological year. Each Canadian province and territory represent a discrete geographic region, except for the provinces comprising Atlantic Canada (New Brunswick, Newfoundland and Labrador, Nova Scotia, and Prince Edward Island), which are grouped into a single region. Similarly, samples from the contiguous United States are grouped into 8 geographic regions, representing the northern and southern halves of each migratory bird flyway (from East to West: Atlantic, Mississippi, Central and Pacific). The histogram (bottom panel) summarises the number of viral genomes collected in each epidemiological month over the outbreak, stratified by viral genotype. These data encompass a total of 84 unique H5Nx genotypes, only those collected more than 200 times over the course of the outbreak (13 genotypes) are represented by unique colours, all others (71 genotypes) are grouped into the category “Other”.

Epidemiological year 2022-2023

The second epidemiological year of HPAI H5 circulation in North America exhibited distinct shifts in detection patterns across seasons and species groups. Waterfowl detections remained high during the autumn migration period but declined more sharply in winter and spring compared to the first year (Figures 23 and 24). Mortality events in geese increased relative to the previous year, while serological data suggested growing levels of H5 and N1 antibody presence in some duck populations. Over the second epidemiological year, HPAI H5 was detected in 111 species of wild birds across 25 families and 14 orders and 12 species of wild mammals across 8 families and 2 orders in Canada and the US.

Figure 23: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections in wild birds reported in North America by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2022-2023. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. For ease, colony-breeding seabirds were defined differently from other continental regions in this report (Box), and include all species from the taxonomic order Charadriiformes, Pelecaniformes, Procellariiformes, Suliformes. Total reports 2,938. See section ‘Surveillance & data quality’ for data sources.

Figure 24: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections in wild birds reported in North America based on birds sampled alive, through banding and hunter-harvested programmes, per wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2022-2023. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Colony-breeding seabirds were defined differently from other continental regions (Box), and include Charadriiformes, Pelecaniformes, Procellariiformes, Suliformes. Total reports 1,430. See section ‘Surveillance & data quality’ for data sources.

In late autumn and early winter, HPAI H5 remained widespread in waterfowl, averaging 680 detections per month (69.6% of all detections) in the US and Canada reported on government dashboards.

Detections occurred across the continent, with detection frequencies highest in the Pacific flyway (30.7%), Mississippi (25.9%) and Central flyways (24.3%) and lowest in the Atlantic flyway (19.2%). A pronounced peak in detections in waterfowl occurred in November, corresponding to outbreaks observed in geese and apparent rising prevalence in live and hunted dabbling ducks. From October to December 2022, large-scale mortality events in geese were documented across North America, often involving hundreds of birds per event. These primarily affected lesser snow goose, Canada goose, and cackling goose, though HPAI mortality was also confirmed in Ross's goose, and greater white-fronted goose. These mortalities were particularly notable in staging areas used by migrating geese. In Mexico, the first isolation of HPAI H5N1 reported by targeted surveillance was detected in a blue-winged teal in October 2022. This was followed by further detections through investigation of mortality events in mallards and blue-winged teal.

During winter, the majority of detections in waterfowl in Canada and the US were in the Atlantic flyway (44.2%), followed by the Central (26.1%), Pacific (18.7%), and Mississippi (11.0%) flyways. Waterfowl detections remained relatively steady through January before declining sharply in February, consistent with post-migration patterns. Unlike the previous year, detections were not evenly distributed between the Central and Pacific Flyways but were more concentrated in the Atlantic Flyway.

During the spring detections in the US and Canada in waterfowl continued to decline. Unlike spring 2022, when waterfowl detections peaked in April, detections in spring 2023 declined sharply in April and into May. This suggests reduced transmission and/or shedding among spring migrants compared to the previous year, potentially due to increases in population immunity.

By the summer, detections in waterfowl in the US and Canada were low (109 detections), with waterfowl comprising 22.9% of detections, most of which were in the Atlantic (56.0%) and Mississippi (32.0%) flyways. Unlike summer 2022, when Pacific flyway detections were more evenly distributed across the season, detections in Summer 2023 were concentrated in August.

Detections began to increase in waterfowl in the US and Canada in the early autumn (September 2023), with a shift in distribution toward the Central (45.0%) and Pacific (40.8%) flyways. Notably, the Pacific flyway experienced a peak in detections before the Central Flyway, suggesting potential differences in epidemiology between regions.

Dabbling ducks continued to show apparently high infection prevalence but were not highly represented in mortality events attributable to HPAI. In Canada, the prevalence of suspect and confirmed HPAI H5 in live and hunted dabbling ducks (predominantly mallards) decreased to approximately 2% (~ 106/4,647) between October 2022 and September 2023 (personal communication, J. Giacinti).

HPAI H5-associated mortality in Canada and the US continued in raptors, occurring as persistent detections of individual or small numbers of detections rather than large-scale mortality events. While there was a decline in absolute number of detections in raptors this year, the proportion of detections in raptors out of all detections in wildlife was higher than the previous year. In the US, black vultures continued to experience elevated mortality through the autumn and winter into early spring.

Unlike in spring 2022, when detections were concentrated in April, raptor detections in spring 2023 were more evenly distributed across the season, likely reflecting reduced acute exposure to large scale avian mortality like occurred in Spring 2022. A single documented outbreak in California condors in Arizona, US, in March and April, 2023 resulted in 20 confirmed mortalities [127].

In Mexico, detections of HPAI H5 in raptors were limited and identified through individual case investigations. The first documented detection occurred in October 2022 in a gyrfalcon owned by a falconer, followed by a positive detection in an American goshawk presented to official veterinary services in November 2022. Both detections were identified in the State of Mexico and were temporally aligned with regional HPAI H5 activity in waterfowl.

HPAI H5 detections in colony-breeding seabirds remained relatively low throughout the second epidemiological year but showed seasonal shifts in both geographic distribution and intensity. Unlike autumn of the previous year, when detections were primarily concentrated in the Atlantic Flyway, most seabird detections during this period were in the Pacific Flyway (55.0%), followed by the Atlantic Flyway (32.9%). The average monthly detection rate was approximately 50 detections per month, which was slightly higher than the same period in the previous year. During winter, detections in the US and Canada were made primarily in the Atlantic Flyway (69.8% of detections). During spring of this epidemiological year most detections were recorded in the Atlantic flyway (81.0%) and unlike the previous year, there were no large-scale early-season mortality events documented in 2023. The number of reported detections in colony-breeding seabirds remained relatively low during the summer, and most of those occurred in the Pacific flyway (72.7%).

During the summer of 2023, Caspian terns in the Pacific flyway experienced population-level impacts due to a significant outbreak among this species on Rat Island (Washington, US) [128]. The colony, estimated at 1,800–1,900 adults, experienced severe losses, with 1,101 adult and 520 chick mortalities, equating to a minimum 56% loss of the breeding population. Extrapolated estimates suggest 10–14% of the Pacific flyway population was lost.

A notable example of antibody testing results is from northern gannets at Bonaventure Island, Quebec, Canada, where no anti-NP antibodies were detected in eggs in 2022, aligning with subsequent colony-wide HPAI-related mortality [129]. By 2023, however, 40% of gannet eggs tested positive for anti-influenza nucleoprotein antibodies, and 50% for anti-H5 antibodies, suggesting that individuals were exposed to and survived infection. Similarly, common eiders had high anti-H5 antibody prevalence in 2023, indicating recent and widespread H5 AIV exposure. In contrast, some species, such as black-legged kittiwakes and northern fulmars, exhibited anti-NP antibodies but lacked detectable anti-H5 antibodies, suggesting exposure to non-H5 lineages or more rapid waning of anti-H5 antibodies.

During this epidemiological year detections were made in terrestrial mammals across all four flyways in relatively low numbers. More frequent detections were recorded during winter (~27 per month) and spring (~31 per month) in the US and Canada which was temporally associated with increased detections in waterfowl. The rate of detections in terrestrial mammals decreased during summer and autumn. There were no reported detections in marine mammals until the summer of this epidemiological year with a small mortality event in harbour seals (16 confirmed) in the US state of Washington [128]. Although overall detection rates remained low in wild mammals, the increase in detections in terrestrial carnivores during late winter and early spring mirrored trends in avian mortality, supporting the hypothesis that scavenging plays a key role in transmission.

HPAI H5 genotype B3.2 was the predominant genotype circulating at the end of the prior epidemiological year (September 2022) in Alaska, US [126] as well as in October 2022 in the prairie pothole region of Canada (Figure 22). These regions are amongst the most prominent waterfowl breeding grounds globally and both overlap with all four North American migratory flyways. Therefore, the predominance of genotype B3.2 in these regions during the autumn migratory period for waterfowl likely facilitated spread of this genotype latitudinally and longitudinally [125]. Subsequently, genotype B3.2 became the predominant genotype in every geographic region of North America, aside from the Canadian territories and the Atlantic regions of the US. In the Atlantic US, a diverse set of wholly Eurasian lineage and reassortant viruses were circulating during this epidemiological year and included another presumed trans-Atlantic incursion (A5) that remained localized within the northeast Atlantic. Detections in the Canadian territories (i.e., Yukon, Northwest Territories, Nunavut) were rare over this period, as only a single virus was detected in each territory, each of a different genotype (Figure 22).

A trans-Atlantic incursion of HPAI H5N5 (A6) was also detected during this epidemiological year. While few detections of HPAI H5N5 were recorded (43 in Canada and 4 in the US in GISAID), this genotype was detected in a higher proportion of mammals than H5N1 and no reassortment with local viruses has been detected.

Epidemiological year 2023-2024

During the third epidemiological year, HPAI H5 was detected in 100 species of wild birds across 28 taxonomic families and 14 orders and 12 species of wild mammals across 10 taxonomic families and 4 orders in Canada and the US.

In late autumn and early winter there was a relatively high number of detections in waterfowl in the US and Canada averaging 733 detections per month (86.3% of all detections) (Figures 25 and 26). This was lower than autumn 2022 (~980 per month) (Figures 23 and 24). Localised mortality events in geese were reported but not as extensive or severe as the outbreaks seen in the previous year. During winter, reported detections in the US and Canada decreased to 253 detections per month, with a notable geographic shift toward the Atlantic Flyway (68.5%). This contrasts with the previous winter, when detections were more evenly distributed across flyways. By spring, reported detections in waterfowl in the US and Canada fell to 11.7 detections per month which is lower than previous years. During summer, only five detections were recorded in waterfowl the US and Canada. During early autumn (September 2024), reported detections in waterfowl in the US and Canada had increased again (29 detections).

In Mexico, detections of HPAI H5 in waterfowl during this period were limited and identified through active/targeted surveillance activities. Live bird surveillance detected infections in a cinnamon teal in October 2023 and a northern pintail in November 2023 in Jalisco, while hunter-harvest surveillance identified detections in northern shovelers in December 2023 and February 2024, and in two blue-winged teal in March 2024, all in Yucatán. These detections occurred within the broader seasonal window of waterfowl-associated activity observed across North America.

Figure 25: Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus morbidity/mortality surveillance detections in wild birds reported in North America by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2023-2024. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. For ease, colony-breeding seabirds were defined differently from other continental regions in this report (Box), and include all species from the taxonomic order Charadriiformes, Pelecaniformes, Procellariiformes, Suliformes. Total reports 3,912. Total reports 1,522. See section ‘Surveillance & data quality’ for data sources.

Figure 26. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections in wild birds reported in North America based on birds sampled alive, through banding and hunter-harvested programmes, per wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2023-2024. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. For ease, colony-breeding seabirds were defined differently from other continental regions in this report (Box), and include all species from the taxonomic order Charadriiformes, Pelecaniformes, Procellariiformes, Suliformes. Total reports 2,179. See section ‘Surveillance & data quality’ for data sources.

Reported detections in raptors were distributed across all flyways in this epidemiological year with some geographical variation across the seasons and numbers of detections generally lower than the previous year. In the United States and Canada, detections continued to occur primarily as sporadic detections rather than large-scale mortality events, with patterns consistent with reduced exposure to mass avian die-offs relative to earlier years.

In Mexico, raptor detections were likewise identified through individual case investigations and localised mortality events. In October 2023, a resident breeding laughing falcon was found dead on Lobos Island, Veracruz, and subsequently tested positive for HPAI H5N1; this detection occurred in the context of a broader mortality event involving at least 150 unidentified species associated with marine and estuarine environments. Additional raptor detections were reported in November 2023 in Baja California, where a Cooper’s hawk (*Accipiter cooperii*) and a vulture from a rural area tested positive for HPAI H5N1.

Reported detections in colony-breeding seabirds were made on both the Atlantic and Pacific flyways in relatively low numbers across the seasons of this epidemiological year. Unlike previous years, where seabird mortality peaked during the breeding season, no major mortality events were documented in summer 2024 and detections remained lower than in both 2022 and 2023.

The seasonal trend of detections of HPAI H5 in wild mammals in this epidemiological year mirrored previous years, where terrestrial mammal detections peaked in spring, aligning with increased avian mortality, and declined through the summer and autumn. Marine mammal detections remained sporadic, with no large-scale outbreaks observed in 2024.

The beginning of this epidemiological year marked the widespread detection of viruses assigned to genotype B3.6 (Figure 22). Genotype B3.6 was inferred to have emerged in the prairie pothole region, Canada, just prior to the autumn migratory period, which facilitated latitudinal and longitudinal dispersal [125].

This mirrored the events of the previous epidemiological year, wherein the ancestral genotype B3.2 dispersed in a similar fashion. B3.6 became the predominant genotype along the Mississippi, Central and Pacific flyways. Two notable exceptions were British Columbia, Canada and Alaska, US, which saw a resurgence of Eurasian lineage viruses (genotype A3) and a reassortant virus (B3.10) that was largely confined to British Columbia. Late in this epidemiological year, another reassortant viral genotype, D1.1, emerged within this region that was descended from genotype A3. Much like previous epidemiological years, the genotypes circulating in the Atlantic flyway were distinct from all others.

The genotypic diversity of viruses observed circulating along the Atlantic flyway in the previous year was largely replaced by a new reassortant virus (C2.1) and the reemergence of wholly Eurasian lineage viruses, primarily genotype A2 (Figure 22). Additional H5N5 sequences are available in GISAID from this epidemiological year (32 Canada, 6 US).

Analysis of clade 2.3.4.4b HA genes from H5N1 viruses collected in Mexico between 2022 and 2024 revealed limited genetic variation in 2022. The isolates were primarily associated with the Central and Mississippi Flyway migratory routes, suggesting viral dispersal linked to migratory wild birds. The most frequently detected substitution among these isolates was L131Q in the HA1 subunit, as it was present in most of the analysed sequences from both the Central and Mississippi flyways. This substitution is in a region close to antigenic domains and has been previously reported in clade 2.3.4.4 viruses, suggesting it is pervasive within this lineage. No mutations associated with changes in receptor specificity ($\alpha 2,6$) or substitutions previously linked to mammalian adaptation were detected.

Furthermore, the molecular profile observed in HA was consistent with highly pathogenic viruses well-adapted to avian hosts, with no evidence of marked selective pressure toward new biological phenotypes. Overall, the results indicate that the analyzed viruses H5N1 HPAI clade 2.3.4.4b showed a conserved genetic evolution of the HA gene during the evaluated period.

Surveillance and data quality

In Canada and the United States there are two main surveillance components:

1. Surveillance of apparently healthy wild birds. This entails live and hunter-harvested bird surveillance concentrated on waterfowl populations and largely in collaboration with bird banding programmes and recreational hunting activities. This surveillance component is effective at detecting infection in apparently healthy individuals, including reservoirs for transmission and spread, while providing opportunities for targeted sampling in species of conservation concern, areas under-sampled by surveillance of sick, injured or dead birds, and interfaces between wildlife, domestic animals, humans, and the environment, that are important from One Health perspectives.
2. Surveillance of wildlife found dead, sick or injured. This surveillance component is effective at identifying causes of morbidity and mortality in susceptible wildlife across broad spatiotemporal scales. Surveillance occurs year-round; however, detection and submission efforts fluctuate geographically and seasonally, often aligning with human population density and accessibility.

Canada's Interagency Surveillance Program for Avian Influenza Viruses in Wildlife involves federal agencies including Environment and Climate Change Canada, Canadian Food Inspection Agency, Public Health Agency of Canada, Indigenous Services Canada, Polar Knowledge Canada, Parks Canada, and Fisheries and Oceans Canada; and provincial and territorial governments; Indigenous governments, communities, and organizations; academic institutions; and organizations such as the Canadian Wildlife Health Cooperative. Since autumn 2021, an interagency working group has convened to discuss and plan surveillance activities, including outlining an implementation plan which is publicly available [5].

All detections of HPAI are reported on publicly available websites in as close to real-time as possible [130] and viral sequences are uploaded to public repositories, such as the Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID [131]).

In the United States, wildlife surveillance for HPAI is coordinated by the Interagency Steering Committee for Avian Influenza Surveillance in Wild Migratory Birds involving United States Department of Agriculture, United States Fish and Wildlife Service, United States Geological Survey, Tribal Nationals, and the National Flyway Councils, and includes participation from a broad network of private, nonprofit, local, and academic partners [132]. All detections are reported on publicly available websites in as close to real-time as possible (e.g., [127] and [133]), though resource limitations combined with large surges of suspect cases can lead to time lags in reporting. Viral sequences are also made publicly available as rapidly as possible to Genbank and GISAID.

In Mexico, surveillance of wild birds began in October 2014, funded by a grant awarded to the Mexico–United States Commission for the Prevention of Foot and Mouth Disease and other Exotic Diseases of Animals (CPA-DGSA-SENASICA) by the USDA-ARS for the surveillance and control of Newcastle Disease and Avian Influenza (Project No. 5612-32000-064-18S).

Since then, a small team of biologists has actively monitored live wild birds across the country characterizing the viral diversity of wintering waterfowl along Mexico's three major flyways. Reports of dead birds are also investigated by the CPA's official veterinary services based on notifications from municipal environmental and rural development agencies. While wildlife reporting is not common in Mexican society, federal and state wildlife agencies support CPA by providing waterfowl harvested by hunters.

Surveillance limitations

HPAI surveillance in North American wildlife is conducted independently by each country. While existing surveillance programmes provide valuable insights, several limitations must be considered when interpreting data. Surveillance efforts vary significantly by region, species, and methodology, leading to gaps in coverage and inconsistencies in data comparability. In North America, waterfowl dominate live captured and hunter-harvested sampling, while non-waterfowl species remain underrepresented and primarily sampled by academic groups. Mortality surveillance is opportunistic, relying on public reporting and localized outbreak investigations, which introduces a detection bias.

Surveillance capacity is unevenly distributed across regions, with differences in infrastructure, personnel, reporting structures, and funding affecting sample collection and outbreak response. Short-term or reactive funding cycles often result in piecemeal monitoring efforts rather than sustained, long-term surveillance. These limitations impact our ability to assess prevalence over time, detect early warning signals, and evaluate long-term population effects of HPAI in wildlife.

Central America, the Caribbean and South America

Introduction

High pathogenicity avian influenza H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b (HPAI H5N1) was first detected in South America in October 2022 (Colombia), while Central America reported its first detections in December 2022 (Panama) and the Caribbean in February 2023 (Cuba) (Annex I). In Central America, the virus caused relatively minor outbreaks in wild birds (mostly pelicans) until about March 2023. However, the virus spread widely in South America, particularly affecting marine species along the Pacific and Atlantic coastlines. In this region, the epidemic peaked during 2023, with only a few relatively minor outbreaks reported in 2024 in three countries (WAHIS). All countries with HPAI outbreaks in 2022-2024 experienced outbreaks in both domestic birds (commercial poultry and /or backyard birds) and wildlife (WAHIS).

Two outstanding features of the HPAI epidemic in South America were the severe impacts on colony-breeding seabirds, particularly along the Pacific coastline, and the first detection of mammal-to-mammal transmission in pinnipeds facilitating rapid and massive spread across multiple countries both along the Pacific and the Atlantic shorelines [134, 135].

Spread patterns and impacts

Epidemiological year 2022-2023

Central America and the Caribbean

Between late 2022 and March 2023, HPAI caused outbreaks in Central America, mostly restricted to brown pelicans, which died in their hundreds. Following the first detection for the region in December 2022 in Panama [136] and [137], detections were reported by Costa Rica [138] and Guatemala [139] in January 2023. In February 2023, HPAI H5 was reported in several captive wild birds at the Zoological Garden of Havana, Cuba [140].

South America

In South America, there were severe outbreaks of HPAI reported between October 2022 and December 2023. Phylogenetic analyses indicate multiple independent introductions of HPAI H5Nx 2.3.4.4b genotype B3.2 viruses to South America from North America between October and November 2022: Perú, Colombia, Ecuador, and Venezuela [135, 141-144]. B3.2 viruses are 4:4 reassortants of Eurasian H5 lineage (PA, HA, NA, and MP) and LPAI viruses from the North American lineage (PB2, PB1, NP, and NS) [143, 145]. This genotype was dominant in North America in late 2022, was detected across all flyways, and was particularly prevalent in waterfowl. The genotype was last detected in North America in December 2023 [116], but remained the only recorded genotype in South American throughout the reporting period.

The epidemic spread in South America accelerated by spring (Figure 27), November 2022, when viruses from Peru and Chile expanded to other countries in two main directions, southwards along the Pacific coast, and eastwards across the Andes. Initially, the epidemic affected very large numbers of colony-breeding seabirds (pelicans, boobies, cormorants) and included several bird-to-mammal spillover events, with multiple detections in pinnipeds and isolated detections in cetaceans [141]. Around summer, February 2023, however, a divergent marine mammal subclade emerged from wild bird viruses from Peru and Chile, and later spread across five countries (Peru, Chile, Argentina, Uruguay, and Brazil) on both the Pacific and Atlantic coasts of South America [134, 146]. The emergence of the 'marine mammal subclade' was associated with high numbers of fatal infections in marine mammals. This virus subclade possesses multiple PB2 mutations linked to mammalian adaptation, caused the only known human case in Chile (reportedly from environmental exposure), and spilled back numerous times into seabirds, particularly terns (*Sterna* spp.) [134, 135, 146-151]. Notably, there was sustained mammal-to-mammal transmission of this clade in pinnipeds, leading to severe mortality events, such as the mass mortality of southern elephant seals at Península Valdés, Argentina in spring (October 2023), that killed over 17,000 newborn pups [134, 152]. On the other hand, the monophyletic avian subclade viruses from Peru and Chile spread in poultry and wild birds (mostly waterfowl) eastward across the continent, starting around January 2023. This avian clade virus reached Argentina (inland), Bolivia, Uruguay, Paraguay, Brazil, and eventually arrived at the distant subantarctic islands of South Georgia/Islas Georgias del Sur in October 2023 in the Southwest Atlantic Ocean [134, 153-159]. As was predicted due to connectivity of wildlife populations [160], this spread in the Southwest Atlantic led to the incursion into Antarctica, where the virus arrived in January 2024 (see Antarctica section, this report).

The spread of HPAI in South America has not been clearly associated with wild bird migrations beyond introductions to the continent. The spread of viruses in the avian subclade across the Andes and inland in southern South America in early 2023 may have been linked to regional and local waterfowl seasonal migration.

The spillover and emergence of the marine mammal subclade may have been facilitated by breeding aggregations of South American sea lions and fur seals coinciding in space and time with massive outbreaks in breeding seabirds. However, the rapid spread of the divergent marine mammal viruses southward along the Pacific and then northward along the Atlantic extended through the autumn and winter and did thus not overlap with sea lion or fur seal breeding seasons. Only elephant seals were affected during breeding, possibly because they are nearly exclusively pelagic and their breeding in late winter-early spring coincided with significant spread among sea lions, and later in seabirds.

The peak of HPAI H5 outbreaks in wildlife in South America occurred between late 2022 and the end of 2023 as the virus spread through susceptible populations [161]. Most of the recorded mortality was in seabirds and marine mammals from Peru and Chile, but significant death tolls for these groups were also recorded in Argentina, Uruguay and Brazil. In addition, some freshwater species like black-necked swans were affected in Chile, Uruguay and southern Brazil [154, 157, 162]. Likewise, mortalities of puna (James's) flamingos were recorded in Argentina [163]. In September 2023, HPAI was detected for the first time in the Galápagos Archipelago, where it killed a relatively small number of great frigatebirds and red-footed boobies (WAHIS). Both great and magnificent frigatebirds were significantly affected in coastal areas of mainland Ecuador and Peru (WAHIS 2024).

Figure 27. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in South American countries that regularly reported (Chile and Brazil) by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2022-2023. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reports 475. Data source: WAHIS.

Epidemiological year 2023-2024

No detections of HPAI were reported in Central America or the Caribbean in 2024, with the exception of a brief outbreak of H5N1 genotype D1.3 viruses in backyard poultry in Puerto Rico in December 2024 [164].

In South America, only three countries: Argentina, Brazil, and Peru, reported detections in wildlife in 2024, all in the first half of the year. No further detections were reported from wildlife during or after the austral winter of 2024 (Figure 28). In southern Argentina, isolated HPAI detections were identified in resident species of seabirds and pinnipeds up to February 2024 [146] (Vanstreets et al. in preparation).

Brazil reported several isolated HPAI detections in birds along its southeastern coast until May 2024, mostly involving terns. Of note, two cross-hemisphere migrants, the common tern (9 detections) and the Manx shearwater (1 case) tested positive, indicating a potential for transhemispheric connectivity [165, 166].

Peru reported outbreaks in wild birds along its central and northern coast until April 2024, mostly affecting Peruvian pelicans with mortality ranging from one to 49 individuals (CNEPCE 2024) [166]. No other countries reported outbreaks in wildlife, though Ecuador and Colombia had detections in backyard poultry in late 2024 (ICA 2024, PAHO 2024) [167] and Peru reported detections in poultry on a nearly monthly basis throughout the year, indicating continued virus circulation in the country [166].

Overall, the testing, detection and public reporting of HPAI in wildlife in South America has lagged considerably in 2024, although the continued detection of HPAI in backyard poultry in several countries suggests continued virus circulation. Possibly because of fewer outbreaks, in 2024 most countries no longer share information on wildlife detections via public databases as was done during 2022-23.

Figure 28. Temporal distribution of the total number of HPAI virus detections reported in South American countries that regularly reported (Chile and Brazil) by week of suspicion (dates indicate the first day of the week) and affected wild bird categories in epidemiological year 2023-2024. Numbers in brackets in the figure legends indicate the number of HPAI virus detections per bird category. Total reports 51. Data source: WAHIS.

Impacts

In terms of the impact of HPAI H5N1 in the region, the virus caused outbreaks (several hundred birds) in Central America, where the species most affected were brown pelicans [161]. The scale of mortality in South America was far greater, where HPAI had devastating impacts on wildlife, especially on seabirds and marine mammals. Up until September 2024, the deaths of over 650,000 birds of at least 82 species and about 52,000 mammals of at least 10 species had been recorded, with the bulk of known mortality occurring in Peru and Chile. The most affected species were South American sea lions (~32,000, 9% of the Peru-Chile population), southern elephant seals (~17,000, 97% of pups born in 2023), South American fur seals (~1,500, 15% Uruguay population), cormorants (*Phalacrocoracidae*) (~262,000), Peruvian boobies (~242,000), Peruvian pelicans (~62,000, 36% of the Perú population), Humboldt penguins (~4,000, 13% of the Chile population), various species of gulls (*Larus* spp.) (~7,000), terns (Inca terns, South American terns and *Thalasseus* spp.) (~3,500), frigatebirds (*Fregata* spp.) (~7,000) and puna (James's) flamingos (~250 individuals) [160, 161, 168, 169]. These numbers undoubtedly represent only a fraction of the total mortality and quantifiable impact will be estimated in future monitoring.

For example, while the mortality rate in adult elephant seals during the 2023 outbreak in Argentina is unknown, 56-67% fewer females and 82% fewer weaned pups (indicative of females already departed) were counted during the annual survey of the breeding colony in 2024 [170]. Similarly, monitored South American sea lion populations in Argentina experienced decreases of approximately 25% as a result of HPAI [171].

Beyond species affected by mass mortalities, the host range of HPAI in South America was wide and included species of conservation concern. HPAI was confirmed in marine otter, southern river otter, Chilean dolphin, common dolphin, spiny porpoise, dusky dolphin, and several species of raptors, vultures, ducks, swan, geese, egrets, grebes, and shorebirds [161]. HPAI was also detected in migratory seabirds and shorebirds found dead in non-breeding areas along the coast of South America, including waved albatross in Peru, elegant tern, sanderling, sooty shearwater, southern giant petrel and black-browed albatross in northern Chile, common tern, Manx shearwater, white-chinned petrel and Antarctic prion in Brazil [160]. This raises concern about their potential role in carrying the virus to distant sites where they aggregate to breed. While the virus reached the Galápagos Islands, which are home to numerous endemic seabirds and marine mammals, only a few great frigatebirds and red-footed boobies were confirmed infected in 2023 [161]. Efforts to identify exposure in other species, such as the critically endangered waved albatross showed negative results [172].

The 2022-23 epidemic of HPAI is the largest recorded mortality event impacting marine wildlife in South America, with as yet unquantified direct and indirect consequences for biodiversity. Particularly notable is the impact on marine mammals, many of which are either recovering from historical population declines or remain endangered [173]. The extent to which different species were impacted appears to result from a combination of species distribution, habitat use, and timing (e.g., virus introduction during breeding aggregation), in addition to other potential species-specific susceptibility to the virus [174].

Surveillance and data quality

Surveillance for avian influenza in wildlife in Central America, the Caribbean and South America is mainly based on testing wildlife found dead, though some countries combine this with some level of testing live wild animals, e.g. sampling in the areas surrounding affected poultry flocks or facilities during outbreaks or regular sampling (including environmental sampling) to provide evidence of freedom from disease [175, 176]. During the epidemic, government agencies developed case definitions and protocols for testing of wildlife. For example, mortality events were investigated if they affected three or more individuals of the same species at the same location and time, and particularly when they involved a novel species or a new location. Frequently, after confirmation of HPAI, further detections in the same species and sites were considered positive based on epidemiological context and were not sampled or tested. Thus, both numerator and denominator data of officially reported wildlife detections were not accurate for estimating the level of mortality due to HPAI.

Few countries linked veterinary services with wildlife managers or experts to survey impacts in wildlife via field counts, contributing to underestimates of mortalities reported to WAHIS [160, 161] (Vanstreels and Uhart, in prep). Monitoring of impacted populations will be required for years into the future to support recovery and management, particularly of threatened species.

Data availability for HPAI in wildlife differs significantly by country with more timely reporting (e.g. on government websites) up to the end of 2023. Efforts to make data publicly accessible were significantly reduced during 2024 across the region. The Panamerican Health Organization (PAHO, [177]) collates and summarizes data on HPAI in both human and animal detections for the Americas in periodic reports. For animals, WOAAH regularly publishes global HPAI Situation Reports, with some degree of regional breakdown (WOAH, [178]).

Maintaining ongoing surveillance for HPAI in wildlife is required to manage the threat of HPAI in future, accompanied by sufficient capacity for outbreak response.

Antarctica

Introduction

Seasonal factors have strong influence on the ecology of wildlife populations in the Antarctic region (Annex I), with most birds and mammals gathering in the region during the austral summer (especially from October to March) and migrating or dispersing to other regions during the rest of the year [179]. In this context, the epidemiology of HPAI in Antarctic wildlife may be best understood by considering austral summers as successive cycles where virus spread and greatest host-virus interaction occurs.

Spread patterns and impacts

Austral summer of 2023-2024

The first detections of HPAI in the Antarctic region were during the austral summer of 2023-2024, with detections in subantarctic islands in the South Atlantic Ocean and on the Antarctic Peninsula.

South Atlantic Ocean

The Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas) reported HPAI between October and December 2023 in a few isolated detections of southern fulmars and black-browed albatrosses [159, 180]. In January 2024, there was an unusual mortality event from HPAI H5 of at least 3,000 adult and 50,000 chicks of black-browed albatrosses on Steeple Jason Island [181-183], which holds the world's largest breeding colony of black-browed albatrosses (210,000 pairs) [181]. Additionally, Steeple Jason Island also experienced HPAI H5-caused mortality of southern rockhopper penguins, and exposure but limited mortality in brown skuas and striated caracaras [184]. From January to April 2024, several additional sites within the archipelago had confirmed HPAI detections in seabirds and raptors, including significant mortalities of gentoo penguins [180, 183]. The population impacts of these outbreaks are difficult to assess due to the scarcity of annual population monitoring efforts at most sites and the limited precision of the death toll estimates at the most severely impacted sites.

South Georgia (Islas Georgia del Sur) reported HPAI between October 2023 and March 2024 in seabirds and marine mammals [166, 185]. Although archipelago-wide mortality estimates are not available to date, significant mortalities were reported for brown skuas, wandering albatrosses, gentoo penguins, Antarctic fur seals and southern elephant seals [158, 159, 185, 186]. At Bird Island, where wildlife mortality was intensively monitored, brown skuas were the most affected species, experiencing earlier and more severe mortality than other species [158].

Genomic analysis suggests that the viruses that affected wildlife in the Falkland Islands and South Georgia during the austral summer of 2023-2024 were introduced via multiple separate events. Viruses from South Georgia were derived from two introductions, one stemming from an ancestor most closely related to the viruses detected in poultry and wild birds in Argentina in the first half of 2023 and another from viruses detected in marine mammals and seabirds in Argentina in the second half of 2023 [159, 186]. In contrast, the viruses sequenced from the Falkland Islands were derived from several introduction events involving ancestors most closely related to the viruses detected in marine mammals in Argentina in the second half of 2023; some of these introductions apparently occurred directly from South America whilst others appear to have occurred indirectly, via South Georgia [159, 186].

Antarctica

The first confirmed HPAI infection was in a kelp gull found dead on Livingston Island (South Shetland Islands) in January 2024 [187]. In February and March 2024, a number of detections were made at various sites along the Antarctic Peninsula and South Shetland Islands by several research groups and National Antarctic Programmes [188-193].

This concerned mostly skuas, but also southern elephant seals, snowy sheathbills, and Adelie penguins. Additionally, suspected cases were reported in Antarctic shags [194]. A significant mortality of skuas, predominantly South Polar skuas (nearly 50 individuals), was reported at Beak Island (Antarctic Peninsula) [188, 192], which is estimated to represent more than 7% of the species' estimated population in the Antarctic Peninsula [195].

Virus genomic data suggests that there were at least two separate introduction events. The early detection in a kelp gull in the South Shetland Islands involved a virus that was most closely related to strains from marine mammals in Argentina in the second half of 2023, suggesting the introduction occurred from South America to Antarctica independently from the Falkland Islands or South Georgia [187]. However, later detections in dead skuas in the northern Weddell Sea involved viruses that were closely related to viruses from South Georgia, specifically to strains that descended from viruses that had circulated in poultry and wild birds in Argentina in the first half of 2023 [186, 196].

Austral summer of 2024-2025

No HPAI detections were reported in the region from March to August 2024 (austral autumn and winter). It is critical to note that there are few human observers in the region during the austral winter – many bases are unstaffed, and there are no tourist operators. Outbreaks emerged again in the austral spring the South Atlantic Ocean followed by detections in subantarctic islands in the South Indian Ocean and then a myriad of detections along the Antarctic Peninsula during the austral summer. Exceptionally, in this section we will include HPAI detections recorded in early 2025.

HPAI surveillance efforts in the Antarctic region are heavily constrained by navigation conditions and climate, leading most of the sampling to be concentrated in January-February of each year. Hence, although some of the detections mentioned here are from samples collected in early 2025, they may be interpreted as indicative of HPAI distribution in late 2024.

South Atlantic Ocean

The first confirmed HPAI case in the Falkland Islands for the austral summer of 2024-2025 was a gentoo penguin found dead in mid-September 2024. Further confirmed detections were reported at various sites from October 2024 to January 2025, including significant mortalities of gentoo penguins in more than 10 sites (at least 2,300 individuals in total) and southern elephant seals (at least 40 individuals) and a confirmed case in Antarctic tern [180, 197]. In September 2024, the first HPAI detections were reported for Gough Island, on the southern portion of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. Only three brown skuas were found dead, with no further impacts on other species [198].

In South Georgia, the first confirmed HPAI detections of the summer were southern elephant seals found dead in early November 2024 [199], with additional reports of suspected cases in southern elephant seal, Antarctic fur seal, king penguin, giant petrel (*Macronectes* sp.), kelp gull, snowy sheathbill, light-mantled albatross, macaroni penguin, gentoo penguin, Wilson's storm-petrel and leopard seal reported from November 2024 to February 2025 [200, #5876, 201, 202]. Although there is no publicly available data on the number of individuals affected, the reports suggest that HPAI was widespread on the archipelago and caused large-scale mortality events, especially in pinnipeds and king penguins.

South Indian Ocean

The first suspected HPAI case in the South Indian Ocean was a brown skua with clinical signs suggestive of HPAI at Marion Island (Prince Edward Islands) in September 2024 [203]. More mortalities in multiple species were reported from early November to March 2025, though the overall occurrence of mortality slowed significantly in January. HPAI was confirmed in six species: wandering albatross, king penguin, brown skua, southern giant petrel, northern giant petrel, and sooty albatross.

The highest HPAI-associated mortality was observed in wandering albatrosses (at least 150 chicks dead out of approximately 1900 chicks from the 2024 cohort), brown skuas (80 adults dead), and king penguins (120 adults dead) [203, 204].

In October 2024, unusual mortality was reported at Possession Island (Crozet Islands) involving several hundreds of southern elephant seals, tens of king penguins, wandering albatrosses and brown skuas, with HPAI H5 detected in southern elephant seals and king penguins. In November 2024, mortality of southern elephant seals from HPAI H5 also was reported at La Grande Terre (Kerguelen Islands). Other species with suspected cases in Crozet and Kerguelen archipelagos comprised kelp gulls, gentoo penguins, Kerguelen shags and pintado petrels. The population impacts of these outbreaks have yet to be assessed, but southern elephant seals and king penguins appeared most affected [184]. It is expected that HPAI also arrived on Heard Island, which is uninhabited, and HPAI was confirmed on Heard Island one year later following a dedicated mission to investigate [205].

Antarctica

The cause of mortality of hundreds of crabeater seals found dead in the northwestern Weddell Sea in November and December 2024 [199] was attributed to HPAI H5 based on positive testing of crabeater seal carcasses from the same area in January 2025 [206]. Additional mortality events and HPAI detections were recorded at various sites in the Antarctic Peninsula and South Shetland Islands from November 2024 to March 2025, with affected species including Antarctic fur seal, kelp gull, gentoo penguin, pintado petrel, skua, and southern elephant seal [187, 199, 206-210].

The distribution of suspected and confirmed cases suggests the virus spread widely, especially among seabirds, but remained essentially confined to the Antarctic Peninsula and the nearby South Shetland Islands. The population impacts of these outbreaks have yet to be assessed, but it seems that skuas and crabeater seals were most affected [206-208, 210].

Surveillance and data quality

The remoteness and harsh environmental conditions of the Antarctic region pose significant challenges for wildlife health surveillance. Currently, information on HPAI in the Antarctic region has been derived from targeted surveillance efforts conducted by National Antarctic Programmes [187, 189, 194, 207, 208, 210, 211], independent research expeditions [188, 206, 209] and from opportunistic observations of animal carcasses and apparently sick individuals by tour operators or staff based at Antarctic facilities [199, 212]. Data from all of these sources is actively collated and shared on the SCAR HPAI portal [199]. The population impacts of mortality events detected through these, mostly single-day field visits, is difficult to assess because there are no recent population estimates for many affected sites. In the absence of robust and cohesive international HPAI surveillance, the fragmented nature of the data available limits interpretation and understanding of the spread and impacts of HPAI on Antarctic wildlife.

Because Antarctic tourism and research are often focussed on accessible sites and/or charismatic species, there are likely significant biases in the reporting of HPAI detections across space and species. It is likely that current data underrepresents the impacts of HPAI in small bird species and those that nest on cliffs, nunataks (mountain peaks or ridges projecting above a glacier or ice sheet) or other difficult to access sites—e.g. snow petrels, storm petrels (Oceanitidae), southern fulmars, shags (*Leucocarbo* spp.)—when compared to large and charismatic birds breeding in

large colonies that are relatively accessible—e.g. king penguins, brush-tailed penguins (*Pygoscelis* spp.)—and other species that are often closely associated with them—e.g. skuas (*Catharacta* spp.), sheathbills (*Chionis* spp). Similarly, our ability to detect HPAI cases is likely to be poorer for pinnipeds that breed on sea ice and seldom rest on land—e.g. crabeater seals, leopard seals, Ross seals—compared to species that frequently breed on land or haul out near tourist-visited areas and research bases—e.g. fur seals (*Arctocephalus* spp.), southern elephant seals, Weddell seals.

Other challenges in HPAI surveillance in the Antarctic region relate to the biosafety, logistics and governance of efforts to survey wildlife morbidity and mortality and to collect and test samples for HPAI. Concerns on biosafety and the limited access to medical care in Antarctica have constrained feasibility of Antarctic programmes and tourist operators to participate in HPAI surveillance, especially involving the sampling of carcasses or the capture of live birds.

Limited access to laboratory infrastructure in Antarctica is also a restriction to HPAI surveillance, as it often requires the setting up of diagnostic laboratories on vessels or in research stations or the shipping of samples to other continents. In the latter case, obtaining the necessary permits to transport, import and test potentially HPAI-positive samples across national boundaries can be a barrier that further delays or prevents the testing of Antarctic wildlife for this virus.

The global framework for animal health governance is limited when it comes to the reporting and sharing of information about suspected or confirmed HPAI cases in the Antarctic region.

Unlike in other continents, reporting of suspected or confirmed HPAI cases to WOAHA is not mandatory in Antarctica. Also, WOAHA only accepts HPAI reports from national reference laboratories, yet much of the work is performed by researchers who are not part of a national research laboratory. National Antarctic Programmes, researchers and tour operators have been encouraged to report HPAI cases to the Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP), the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR), and the International Association of Antarctica Tour Operators (IAATO). However, this reporting is not mandatory and submitted reports may be held confidentially over concerns on data ownership or perceived impacts to tourism operations. As a result, information on HPAI detections in the Antarctic region is not always made public in a timely manner as occurs in other continents. For these reasons, it is difficult to assess the completeness of the data currently publicly available on HPAI in the Antarctic region, potentially contributing to gaps in our understanding on the epidemiology of HPAI in Antarctic wildlife.

Implementation of surveillance and research to enhance understanding of the epidemiology and impact of HPAI on Antarctic wildlife is required into the future, including on-site diagnostic capacity to enable rapid detection and response. It is also necessary to maintain robust biosafety protocols for human activities (e.g. tourism, research) in the Antarctic region, both to prevent unintentional spread of HPAI and to safeguard human health. Establishment of an international platform for timely sharing of surveillance outputs (e.g. field observations of suspected cases and mortality events, diagnostic results) following standardized diagnostic definitions and transparent review processes will be of benefit to the region.

Oceania

Introduction

At the time of writing, Oceania (Australia, New Zealand, Pacific Islands; Annex I) is the only continental region that remains free from HPAI H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b and other clades of Goose/Guangdong-lineage HPAI H5 viruses. While HPAI H5 clade 2.3.4.4b is not present in Oceania, both LPAI H5 and H7 viruses are present in both Australia and New Zealand and appear to have undergone extended periods of isolation (from both Eurasia, and also each other) [213-

216]. HPAI H7 viruses have emerged repeatedly in Australia, but in all cases, they have evolved from Australian-lineage LPAI H7 viruses [215].

At present, there are three identified potential routes of introduction for clade 2.3.4.4b viruses into Oceania. First, is introduction through long-distance migratory shorebirds and seabirds from the north [217]. Both avian groups have been impacted by HPAI [54, 218]. Millions of shorebirds arrive in Australia each austral spring following migration along the East Asian Australasian Flyway [219, 220], of which approximately 200,000 reach New Zealand. The flyway extends from Alaska and Russia through China, Mongolia, South-east Asia, and Oceania.

In addition to shorebirds, many seabirds breed in Oceania, with very large numbers of Procellariiformes (albatrosses, shearwaters and petrels) breeding in New Zealand. During the non-breeding period these birds migrate as far as the northern Pacific Ocean and off the west coasts of North and South America [221].

The second potential introduction route is through wild duck populations. Most duck species found in Australia and New Zealand are endemic to the Australo-Papuan region [222, 223]. While some species are also present on various islands in the Indo-Malayan archipelago, very few occur west of Wallace's Line.

There is no confirmed evidence that HPAI H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b is currently present east of Wallace's Line [224]. Hence ducks are currently unlikely to introduce HPAI H5N1 2.3.4.4b into Australia or New Zealand, but if HPAI H5 2.3.4.4b spreads further east in the Indo-Malayan archipelago (through poultry trade or wild bird movement), they may play a major role in virus spread through the region.

A third potential introduction route is from the Antarctic region [161]. At the time of writing, HPAI in the Antarctic region has been detected as close to Oceania as Heard Island [205]. From there, seabirds with circumpolar distributions could introduce the virus to Australia and or New Zealand. Alternatively, if outbreaks were to occur on the Antarctic continent closer to Australia and New Zealand, then many species that nest in Oceania and forage on the Antarctic shelf (e.g. short-tailed shearwater) could become infected and potentially spread the virus to Australia.

Spread patterns and impacts

It is plausible that incursion of HPAI H5 into Australia and New Zealand would heavily impact waterfowl, waterbirds and colony-breeding seabirds and raptors, as has been observed on other continents. Approximately ~45% of avian species in Australia and New Zealand are endemic [225], including many species which would likely be susceptible to HPAI, such that widespread outbreaks may have significant impacts on biodiversity in this region.

Surveillance and data quality

Australia has a nationally coordinated targeted surveillance programme for avian influenza viruses in presumed healthy live birds (<https://wildlifehealthaustralia.com.au/Our-Work/Surveillance/Wild-Bird-Surveillance>). The programme is overviewed by a steering group, comprised of state and national animal, environmental and human health government agencies, universities, ecologists, laboratories and poultry and zoo industry stakeholders. This programme involves two streams – a long-standing programme designed to detect and monitor avian influenza viruses circulating in resident wild bird populations, and a more recent programme involving sampling of recently arrived migratory shorebirds and seabirds during the austral summer, to inform risks around incursion of novel avian influenza viruses, including HPAI H5 2.3.4.4b [217, #5853]. Also, there is ongoing surveillance via investigation of unusual disease and mortality events in wildlife populations for probable causes, including HPAI. In October 2024, the Australian Government committed to improving preparedness for HPAI H5 with funding contributions to agricultural, environment and human health agencies [226-228]. Funding includes

allocations to strengthen surveillance and enhance national coordination of response arrangements.

In New Zealand, the Ministry for Primary Industries (MPI) has historically carried out avian influenza surveillance on migratory shorebirds and currently carries out influenza surveillance on resident mallards [229]. MPI also investigates incidents of increased mortality in wild birds for probable causes, including HPAI. The number of incidents reported and investigated has increased in the last two years with the heightened public awareness of HPAI risk. The Ministry for Primary Industries, Department of Conservation, Ministry of Health, and Health New Zealand are working together on objectives regarding HPAI to (1) reduce the impact on native species; (2) reduce the impact on the commercial poultry sector;

(3) maintain supply of poultry meat and eggs to the domestic market and maintain access to overseas markets where possible; and (4) protect human health [230].

While there are no formal surveillance systems or programmes for HPAI in wildlife in Timor Leste, Papua New Guinea or other Pacific island countries and territories, the Australian government supports regular collaborative animal health surveys for priority animal diseases in these countries, including surveillance for avian influenza.

It would be valuable to evaluate of the sensitivity, timeliness and representativeness of surveillance for HPAI in wildlife, to achieve early detection of HPAI in Oceania, including via the Antarctic route. Improvement in sharing of surveillance outputs among countries in Oceania will also benefit countries in the region.

Discussion

The long-distance spread of Goose/Guangdong-lineage HPAI H5 through wildlife populations across multiple continents since 2020 has had unprecedented impacts on wildlife health and welfare. The limited effectiveness of any direct interventions on outbreaks, decades-long recovery times for some populations, and ecosystem-level impacts highlight the need for incorporation of this disease in wildlife conservation and management planning. That a disease generated by poultry farming practices in Asia can threaten the viability of wildlife populations as distant as South America and Antarctica, demonstrates the enormity and holistic nature of the challenge. Improved understanding of the spread and impacts of HPAI H5 on all continents is valuable for those with roles and responsibilities for animal and environmental health worldwide. Surveillance for HPAI needs to support protection of wildlife health, in addition to poultry and public health, and hence changes to objectives, methods, data collection and outputs are required [85]. Here, we have summarised our current understanding of the recent spread and impact of HPAI H5 viruses in wildlife globally, considered limitations in the underlying avian influenza surveillance, and provided recommendations for the future.

From the data reported here, strong variation in spatial and temporal patterns and of mortality in wildlife due to HPAI H5 is clear. In areas where Goose/Guangdong-lineage HPAI H5 has occurred for many years (North Africa, Asia, Europe), there was a key shift in the virus epidemiology in 2020-2021. Specifically, prior to 2020, there were clear seasonal peaks in detections and mortality events in Europe in autumn and winter, associated with repeated incursion of new virus variants [231]. However, in 2021, there was an uncharacteristic continuation of notifications and mortality in the spring and summer months. Phylogenetic analysis indicated continuous circulation at a relatively low prevalence in northwestern Europe and Scandinavia during the summer of 2021. A combination of epidemiological and phylogenetic evidence supported an epidemiological shift to enzootic HPAI virus circulation of HPAI in Europe [59], which preceded spread to North America.

In continents where HPAI H5 was not yet endemic (North America, South America, Antarctica), the patterns of spread and the impacts observed in the first epidemiological year of incursion were different to those in subsequent years. In South America, clear wave-like spread occurred in an

anticlockwise direction (south along the Pacific coast, and north along the Atlantic coast) from November 2022 and through 2023. This coastal spread had devastating impacts on many seabird and marine mammal populations [161].

In both North and South America the magnitude of mortality events appeared to peak in the year of arrival, and tended to decline in subsequent years. It is unclear what drove this pattern but it may have been influenced by: reduction in host population sizes following initial high mortality, increasing immunity in host populations and thus reduction of susceptible individuals, reduction in surveillance activities, and or reduction in reporting.

Seasonal patterns in the life cycles of birds, resulting in periodic high-density aggregations, underpin the epidemiology of HPAI H5 (and all avian influenza viruses). These periodic aggregations are not the same across all wild bird species, and we observed higher HPAI detection patterns in two distinct avian species groups showing aggregation. First, in waterfowl populations there were peaks in detections and apparent prevalence in autumn which is associated with the recruitment of juvenile birds into the population during pre-migration aggregation and autumn migration. This is a well-established trend for LPAI in the populations of these species [232, 233]. Second, HPAI H5 detections and apparent prevalence peaks in the summer in many colony-breeding seabird populations at nesting sites associated with breeding. As with waterfowl, the subsequent recruitment of juvenile birds into the populations at these sites around the time of fledging is also important. These seasonal patterns were most evident in temperate regions *i.e.* Japan, Republic of Korea, much of Europe, Canada and the U.S.

The patterns in southern Africa and West Africa appeared to be different. In these regions, outbreaks occurred in colony-breeding seabirds, but not in waterfowl. The apparent absence of seasonal outbreaks in waterfowl may be due to less regular and more nomadic movement patterns and population dynamics of these species in sub-Saharan Africa, which are largely driven by interannual rainfall patterns [92-94].

Severe mortality events have significantly impacted wild bird and mammalian species on multiple continents, with numerous examples of population and species-level declines directly due to HPAI H5. The impact of HPAI H5 on the affected populations is influenced by factors such as route of exposure to HPAI, mortality rate and reproductive rate of the host, and the impact and mitigation of other factors potentially driving species declines. Raptor species, such as peregrine falcons, are more likely to become infected via eating infected waterbirds even if infection prevalence in their prey populations is very low [69]. Hence these species may continue to be impacted for years after the arrival of the virus in an area. Populations of species that produce fewer offspring per year *i.e.* have a lower reproductive rate (so called K-selected species) such as northern gannets and many other seabirds [65] may take many years to recover from severe discrete mortality events in the year of virus arrival. Recovery may be more rapid in populations of species with higher reproductive rates (so called r-selected species) such as tufted ducks [234]. For many seabird species, other factors such as overfishing, entanglement and climate change are already driving population declines. In cases where such factors can be reduced, the opportunity for population recovery is improved. However, the multitude of interacting threats to population viability of many wild bird and marine mammal species means the additional impact of HPAI could lead to potentially serious consequences in any scenario.

Differences in patterns of spread and impact of HPAI H5 may also be driven by reassortment events with LPAI viruses from local wild bird populations, influencing the susceptibility of species to infection. For example, the higher mortality of black-headed gulls and other gull species in Europe in 2022-23 than in previous years was associated with the emergence of genotype BB viruses, a reassortment of HPAI H5 and a gull-adapted LPAI H13 virus [77].

Mammalian infections have been confirmed on all continents where the virus has been detected, and terrestrial mammals, especially scavengers, and aquatic mammals, especially pinnipeds, have been disproportionately impacted. Most of the mammalian cases are individual infections resulting from bird-to-mammal transmission. However, severe mortality events in pinnipeds in South America and the sub-Antarctic likely are caused by mammal-to-mammal transmission [134,

135] and have significantly impacted populations of South American sea lions and southern elephant seals [152, 235]. The long-term and ecological consequences of these impacts are yet to be determined.

Virus genomic data has been critical in elucidating virus movement patterns, specifically the geographical source of new introductions, the number of introductions to a region, and the independent spread in species groups [125]. For example, viruses detected in great white pelicans in Senegal in 2021 indicated a likely introduction to Africa from Europe; viruses detected in Peru, Ecuador, Columbia and Venezuela in late 2022 showed variation consistent with multiple independent introductions to South America; and a lineage detected in South America in late 2023 showed evidence of adaptation to mammals and apparent spread within marine mammal populations, while a separate lineage continued to spread among wild birds in the same region.

Analyses of these data are also valuable for revealing reassortment events, such as that involving an LPAI virus of gulls in Europe mentioned above, as well as for detecting mutation associated with mammalian adaptation, virulence, and anti-viral resistance.

While serological testing is not a core component of most surveillance programmes for HPAI, serological data has provided critical insights on the spread and impacts of HPAI H5 not evident from virus detection and mortality data. Serology can produce valuable data on population level exposure to HPAI to clarify whether populations have experienced high levels of exposure without obvious mortality, or conversely, whether populations have low antibody prevalence and/or low exposure [236]. For example, serological testing following severe mortality events in northern gannets has shown high frequency of exposure among surviving individuals, and that these birds can subsequently reproduce successfully [65]. High levels of exposure have also been seen in raptors in the U.S., indicating that mortality estimates may be a small proportion of those infected, and that many individuals survive infection [237]. Studies in North America have shown high proportions of exposure to HPAI H5 in duck species that did not experience significant mortality events e.g. mallards in the U.S. and American black ducks in Canada [238, 239]. This has provided valuable information on species more likely involved in long-distance transmission of HPAI. The testing of eggs for HPAI H5 antibodies has also been useful in generating evidence of prior exposure and absence of exposure in various populations of seabird species in Canada [129].

The only continental region not yet affected by HPAI H5 during this reporting period is Oceania [240]. The spread patterns observed in the last five years have implications for understanding potential introduction pathways to Oceania in future. The potential for spread of HPAI H5 via wild birds to Oceania from Asia has long been recognised, but recent events in South America and Antarctica reveal a potential southern introduction pathway not previously considered [161].

This is highlighted by recent detections in the Antarctic region and southern Indian Ocean (Crozet islands, Kerguelen islands and Heard and McDonald Islands) with southern giant petrels, northern giant petrels, brown skuas and kelp gulls identified as species that may have facilitated long-distance spread in the region [184].

Surveillance for HPAI in wildlife involves the systematic collection, collation, analysis and interpretation of relevant data, and timely dissemination of information so that action can be taken [241]. Surveillance activities can be coordinated at a local, national or international level. We found great variation, within and between continents, in publicly available information on surveillance for HPAI in wildlife. Some countries (e.g. Canada, USA and EU member states) have ongoing government-mandated surveillance programmes for HPAI in wildlife with a stated purpose and objectives and public sharing of results, while other areas (e.g. parts of Africa and Asia) appear to lack such surveillance programmes. Determination of performance of animal health surveillance programmes is best achieved through structured scientific evaluations which allow assessment of these programmes against defined attributes [242]. Such evaluations, while being conducted with increasing frequency, are not yet sufficiently shared in the public domain to provide a detailed picture of the capacity and capability of surveillance for HPAI in wildlife among countries and continents. While variation in objectives, sampling approaches and data

management limit comparisons across programmes, we have identified various biases in the representativeness of data generated. For example: most influenza surveillance programmes of apparently healthy wild birds, including those that sample hunted birds, are targeted towards waterfowl, leaving other species groups underrepresented; many influenza surveillance programmes of birds found injured, ill or dead rely on public reporting of sick and dead wildlife, hence areas of higher human population density have much higher sensitivity of surveillance than remote regions. Such biases should be accounted for to allow extrapolation of the surveillance data to the host population level.

Recommendations

We provide some high-level recommendations that we consider important at the international level to: obtain a better assessment of the international spread and impact of HPAI H5 in wildlife populations; translate this knowledge into actions to mitigate the impact of the current HPAI H5 panzootic on wildlife; and reduce the risk of future HPAI emergence events from poultry or other domestic animals to wildlife. We recognise that needs and priorities vary among countries and regions and that this is not a comprehensive list.

For improving surveillance

- Develop collaborative HPAI surveillance programmes (flyway-based where relevant), to provide a year-round picture of HPAI virus dynamics in wildlife populations. Such programmes should aim for equitable sharing of resources (funding, knowledge, laboratories, equipment) among countries involved to enable timely and representative surveillance across the flyways.
- Improve the collection of morbidity and mortality data (e.g. number of sick and dead birds compared to total number of birds present, and species identification, sex, and age categories) associated with HPAI events, including development of an international system for the collation of these data (ideally integrated with existing systems such as WAHIS), to allow estimation of the magnitude of mortality due to HPAI, and hence more accurately inform mitigation and conservation strategies [1, 243, 244].
- Improve public sharing of surveillance data and outputs, including genome sequences of detected HPAI viruses and date, location and wildlife species involved.
- Conduct long-term monitoring of severely impacted wildlife populations, to assess their ability to recover.
- Conduct and publish regular evaluations of surveillance programmes to share information useful for improvement of performance of surveillance in future.

For preparedness and response

- Respond actively to impacts of HPAI on susceptible and affected wildlife populations by increasing their resilience e.g. protecting more wildlife feeding and breeding sites; stricter regulation of fisheries, especially industrial-scale fishing of stocks that have already been determined to be overexploited; reducing wildlife deaths from bycatch in fishing gear; and improving marine planning to minimise further harm to marine wildlife from the development of offshore energy production [245].
- Trial, study and implement short-term response measures to mitigate the impact of HPAI outbreaks in wildlife.
- Develop policies in the poultry sector to prevent HPAI from emerging in poultry (or other livestock) and spilling over into wild birds in order to reduce the risk of future HPAI emergence events in wildlife, domestic animals and humans.

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Annex I. Map showing regions used

Figure Annex I. Map indicating by colouring how this overview has been subdivided per region, roughly per continent. These boundaries are based on the epidemiology and ecology of HPAI H5 and wildlife hosts, and do not reflect any political arrangements or views from the authors or their organizations.

Annex II. List of species names

List of species mentioned in the text with their scientific names (BirdLife International) and IUCN Red List threatened category [8]. Least concern category omitted for clarity.

Birds Common name	Scientific name	IUCN Red List category
Adelie penguin	<i>Pygoscelis adeliae</i>	
African fish eagle	<i>Haliaeetus vocifer</i>	
African jacana	<i>Actophilornis africanus</i>	
African penguin	<i>Spheniscus demersus</i>	Endangered
African sacred ibis	<i>Threskiornis aethiopicus</i>	
American black duck	<i>Anas rubripes</i>	
American crow	<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>	
Antarctic prion	<i>Pachyptila desolata</i>	
Antarctic shag	<i>Leucocarbo bransfieldensis</i>	
Antarctic tern	<i>Sterna vittata</i>	
Barnacle goose	<i>Branta leucopsis</i>	
Black stork	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>	
Black swan	<i>Cygnus atratus</i>	
Black vulture	<i>Coragyps atratus</i>	
Black-billed magpie	<i>Pica hudsonia</i>	
Black-browed albatross	<i>Thalassarche melanophris</i>	
Black-faced spoonbill	<i>Platalea minor</i>	Endangered
Black-headed gull	<i>Chroicocephalus ridibundus</i>	
Black-legged kittiwake	<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>	Vulnerable
Black-necked swan	<i>Cygnus melancoryphus</i>	
Blue crane	<i>Grus paradisea</i>	Vulnerable
Blue jay	<i>Cyanocitta cristata</i>	
Blue-winged teal	<i>Spatula discors</i>	
Brown pelican	<i>Pelecanus occidentalis</i>	
Brown skua	<i>Catharacta antarctica</i>	
Brown-headed gull	<i>Chroicocephalus brunnicephalus</i>	
Cackling goose	<i>Branta hutchinsii</i>	
California condor	<i>Gymnogyps californianus</i>	Critically Endangered
Canada goose	<i>Branta canadensis</i>	
Cape cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax capensis</i>	Endangered
Carrion crow	<i>Corvus corone</i>	
Caspian tern	<i>Hydroprogne caspia</i>	
Chinese crested tern	<i>Thalasseus bernsteini</i>	Critically Endangered
Common crane	<i>Grus grus</i>	
Common eider	<i>Somateria mollissima</i>	
Common kestrel	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	
Common murre	<i>Uria aalge</i>	
Common raven	<i>Corvus corax</i>	
Common shelduck	<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>	
Common tern	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	

Birds Common name	Scientific name	IUCN Red List category
Crested serpent eagle	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	
Curlew sandpiper	<i>Calidris ferruginea</i>	Near Threatened
Dalmatian pelican	<i>Pelecanus crispus</i>	Near Threatened
Double-crested cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>	
Dunlin	<i>Calidris alpina</i>	
Eastern buzzard	<i>Buteo japonicus</i>	
Eastern spot-billed duck	<i>Anas zonorhyncha</i>	
Egyptian goose	<i>Alopochen aegyptiaca</i>	
Elegant tern	<i>Thalasseus elegans</i>	Near Threatened
Eurasian buzzard	<i>Buteo buteo</i>	
Eurasian teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	
Eurasian wigeon	<i>Anas penelope</i>	
Garganey	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	
Gentoo penguin	<i>Pygoscelis papua</i>	
Great black-backed gull	<i>Larus marinus</i>	
Great cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	
Great frigatebird	<i>Fregata minor</i>	
Great skua	<i>Catharacta skua</i>	
Great white pelican	<i>Pelecanus onocrotalus</i>	
Greater crested tern	<i>Thalasseus bergii</i>	
Great white egret	<i>Ardea alba</i>	
Greater white-fronted goose	<i>Anser albifrons</i>	
Grey-crowned crane	<i>Balearica regulorum</i>	Endangered
Grey heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	
Grey-headed gull	<i>Chroicocephalus cirrocephalus</i>	
Gull-billed tern	<i>Gelochelidon nilotica</i>	
Gyr Falcon	<i>Falco rusticolus</i>	
Hadada ibis	<i>Bostrychia hagedash</i>	
Harris's hawk	<i>Parabuteo unicinctus</i>	
Hartlaub's gull	<i>Chroicocephalus hartlaubii</i>	
Herring gull	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	
Hooded crane	<i>Grus monacha</i>	Vulnerable
Hooded crow	<i>Corvus cornix</i>	
House crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	
Humboldt penguin	<i>Spheniscus humboldti</i>	Vulnerable
Inca tern	<i>Larosterna inca</i>	Near Threatened
Kelp gull	<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	
Kerguelen shag	<i>Leucocarbo verrucosus</i>	
King penguin	<i>Aptenodytes patagonicus</i>	
Large-billed crow	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	
Laughing falcon	<i>Herpetotheres cachinnans</i>	
Lesser sand plover	<i>Anarhynchus mongolus</i>	
Lesser scaup	<i>Aythya affinis</i>	
Lesser snow goose	<i>Anser caerulescens</i>	
Light-mantled albatross	<i>Phoebastria palpebrata</i>	Near Threatened

Birds Common name	Scientific name	IUCN Red List category
Little egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	
Macaroni penguin	<i>Eudyptes chrysolophus</i>	Vulnerable
Magnificent frigatebird	<i>Fregata magnificens</i>	
Mallard	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	
Mandarin duck	<i>Aix galericulata</i>	
Manx shearwater	<i>Puffinus puffinus</i>	
Marbled teal	<i>Marmaronetta angustirostris</i>	Vulnerable
Mediterranean gull	<i>Larus melanocephalus</i>	
Mourning collared dove	<i>Streptopelia decipiens</i>	
Mute swan	<i>Cygnus olor</i>	
Northern fulmar	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	
Northern gannet	<i>Morus bassanus</i>	
Northern giant petrel	<i>Macronectes halli</i>	
Northern pintail	<i>Anas acuta</i>	
Northern shoveler	<i>Spatula clypeata</i>	
Peregrine falcon	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	
Peruvian booby	<i>Sula variegata</i>	
Peruvian pelican	<i>Pelecanus thagus</i>	
Pied crow	<i>Corvus albus</i>	
Pintado petrel	<i>Daption capense</i>	
Puna flamingo	<i>Phoenicoparrus jamesi</i>	Near Threatened
Red knot	<i>Calidris canutus</i>	Near Threatened
Red-crowned crane	<i>Grus japonensis</i>	Endangered
Red-footed booby	<i>Sula sula</i>	
Ross's goose	<i>Anser rossii</i>	
Ruff	<i>Philomachus pugnax</i>	
Sanderling	<i>Calidris alba</i>	
Sandwich tern	<i>Thalasseus sandvicensis</i>	
Short-tailed shearwater	<i>Puffinus tenuirostris</i>	
Slender-billed gull	<i>Chroicocephalus genei</i>	
Snow petrel	<i>Pagodroma nivea</i>	
Snowy sheathbill	<i>Chionis albus</i>	
Sooty albatross	<i>Phoebastria fusca</i>	Endangered
Sooty shearwater	<i>Ardenna grisea</i>	Near Threatened
South American tern	<i>Sterna hirundinacea</i>	
South polar skua	<i>Catharacta maccormicki</i>	
Southern fulmar	<i>Fulmarus glacialoides</i>	
Southern giant petrel	<i>Macronectes giganteus</i>	
Southern rockhopper penguin	<i>Eudyptes chrysocome</i>	Vulnerable
Spotted redshank	<i>Tringa erythropus</i>	
Spur-winged goose	<i>Plectropterus gambensis</i>	
Square-tailed nightjar	<i>Caprimulgus fossii</i>	
Steller's sea eagle	<i>Haliaeetus pelagicus</i>	Vulnerable
Striated caracara	<i>Phalcoboenus australis</i>	Near Threatened
Wandering albatross	<i>Diomedea exulans</i>	Vulnerable

Birds Common name	Scientific name	IUCN Red List category
Waved albatross	<i>Phoebastria irrorata</i>	Critically Endangered
West African crested tern	<i>Thalasseus albididorsalis</i>	(not evaluated)
Whiskered tern	<i>Chlidonias hybrida</i>	
White stork	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	
White-chinned petrel	<i>Procellaria aequinoctialis</i>	Vulnerable
White-faced whistling duck	<i>Dendrocygna viduata</i>	
White-naped crane	<i>Grus vipio</i>	Vulnerable
White-tailed eagle	<i>Haliaeetus albicilla</i>	
Whooper swan	<i>Cygnus cygnus</i>	
Wilson's storm-petrel	<i>Oceanites oceanicus</i>	
Wood duck	<i>Aix sponsa</i>	
Yellow-billed duck	<i>Anas undulata</i>	
Yellow-legged gull	<i>Larus michahellis</i>	